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Reception Policies, Practices and Responses

Greece Country Report

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List of abbreviations

AAU: Autonomous Asylum Units

AIDA: Asylum Information Database

AMIF: Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund

AMKA: Social security number

CEAS: Common European Asylum System

DYEP: Programme of afternoon preparatory classes (*Δομές Υποδοχής και Εκπαίδευσης Προσφύγων*)

EASO: European Asylum Support Office

ECHR: European Court of Human Rights

ESTIA: Emergency Support to Integration and Accommodation program

FILOXENIA: Temporary Shelter and Protection for the Most Vulnerable Migrants in Greece

FRS: First Reception Service

GCA: Greece Cash Alliance

GCR: Greek Council of Refugees

IOM: International Organisation for Migration

KEELPNO: Centre for Disease Control and Prevention

LGBTQI: Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, Intersex

NGOs: Non-Governmental Organisations

PHILOS: Emergency health response to refugee crisis

RAO: Regional Asylum Office

RIC: Reception and Identification Centre

RIS: Reception and Identification Service

SGBV: Sexual Based Violence

SSI: Social Solidarity Income

TCN: Third Country Nationals

UNHCR: United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

About the project

RESPOND is a Horizon 2020 project which aims at studying the multilevel governance of migration in Europe and beyond. The consortium is formed of 14 partners from 11 source, transit and destination countries and is coordinated by Uppsala University in Sweden. The main aim of this Europe-wide project is to provide an in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration at macro, meso and micro levels through cross-country comparative research and to critically analyse governance practices with the aim of enhancing the migration governance capacity and policy coherence of the EU, its member states and third countries.

RESPOND will study migration governance through a narrative which is constructed along five thematic fields: (1) Border management and security, (2) Refugee protection regimes, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanization. Each thematic field reflects a juncture in the migration journey of refugees and is designed to provide a holistic view of policies, their impacts and responses given by affected actors within.

In order to better focus on these themes, we divided our research question into work packages (WPs). The present report is concerned with the findings related to WP4, which focuses specifically on reception policies, practices and humanitarian responses to the current refugee crisis. Despite efforts to achieve harmonization (especially promoted by the 2016 CEAS and by the ENP), relevant differences exist in this field in the countries that are the object of research (Austria, Denmark, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Sweden, UK, Turkey and Lebanon). WP4 will map the policies and practices of reception and humanitarian responses in the aforementioned countries and the perceptions, actions and reactions of migrants to policies and practices. The main objectives of WP4 are as follows:

- to develop a mapping of policies and practices of reception in the countries being researched;
- to develop a typology of these policies, practices and responses
- to assess the coherence of these policies and practices with respect to international and EU standard
- to study the perceptions, actions and reactions of migrants to policies and practices
- to provide basic information in the area of reception for the development of all subsequent WPs.

The last point will be achieved through an additional comparative report that will be based on the data from individual country reports.

Executive summary/Abstract

This report is part of the fourth Work Package of RESPOND (WP4) and deals with the issues of refugee reception. The main goal of the report is to present and discuss the legislative measures and policies, the reception practices followed by state and non-state agencies and the experiences of asylum-seekers with regards to reception in Greece. The report focuses on refugee reception policies in the period 2011-2018 and on reception practices since 2015.

The term “refugee reception” is used to refer to the EU’s ensemble of legislation, policies, implementation practices, institutions and actors concerned with defining, conceptualising and implementing reception in the EU Member States and specifically Greece. Even though the time frame of “reception” is not clearly defined in EU legislation, for the purpose of RESPOND programme reception refers to the liminal period between the arrival and application for asylum and the issuing of a decision on the asylum application.

The research methodology implemented for the needs of this report – and of the overall RESPOND programme – combined diverse methods. The review of the national legislation on issues of refugee reception was accompanied by a review of a series of reports by national and international organizations and NGOs, as well as European and national official documents. The practices of reception are analysed on the basis of the empirical material assembled during the field qualitative research, which was conducted in Lesbos and Athens from June 2018 to December 2018 at a meso and micro level. The meso level included 15 semi-structured interviews with executives and employees of the authorities, international organizations and NGOs. Additionally, a round-table discussion organised by the University of the Aegean working group in November 2018 provided crucial insights to the research. As for the micro level, 34 semi-structured interviews were conducted with refugees living in Moria Hotspot and in Athens, including a focus-group interview.

The report is divided into 5 sections, including introduction, methodology and conclusions. The third section presents the “Policies and Legal Regulations of Reception” and significant recent developments such as the adoption of Law 4540/2018 that amended the Greek legislation in accordance with the provisions of Directive 2013/33/EU on the standards required for the reception of applicants for international protection.

The section entitled “Practices of Reception” analyses the different types of accommodation and housing; the practices of early access to education and the labour market; the services and allowances provided; and the encounter with officials, civic actors and the receiving society. Extended analysis has been provided particularly for the section of accommodation and housing as the serious shortcomings on accommodation affect significant other aspects of reception.

A wide range of problems related to all aspects of reception emerge from the analysis. The accommodation conditions in Northeastern Aegean islands remain inhuman, due to the significant overcrowding, while the accommodation in mainland camps usually established outside the urban environment, result in the spatial segregation of the asylum-seekers. Accommodation in the urban space through the UNHCR accommodation scheme “ESTIA” can be highlighted as a good practice, but it should be expanded to host a larger number of asylum-seekers and not just the vulnerable categories of the respective population. As regards education, despite the progress made on the implementation of the DYEP

programme, low rates of school attendance among migrant children still exist. Concerning employment, a wide range of administrative obstacles that asylum seekers face may lead to undeclared employment or unemployment.

Furthermore, there are still serious problems regarding Services and Allowances in terms of access to health care and medical and psychosocial support, especially in the Hotspots on the Northeastern Aegean islands but also in camps in the mainland. As regards to the provision of food and non-food items especially in the Hotspots, even basic needs such as food, hygiene products and blankets are often not covered. Additionally, in terms of services and allowances, the poor Greek welfare state that was also affected by the austerity measures during the crisis has proven inadequate to cover the relevant needs. Additionally, crucial observations regarding the relations of asylum-seekers with the receiving society are highlighted, as they range from a “welcome” culture of solidarity to racist practices and violence that prevail in the country until today.

The report concludes with crucial observations on the in the implementation, experiences and practices applied in the field of refugee reception, which can vary depending on the site, the point in time and the actors involved. The report closes with certain policy recommendations that emerged as a result of the present research.

Introduction

The term “refugee reception” is used to refer to the EU’s ensemble of legislation, policies, implementation practices, institutions and actors concerned with defining, conceptualising and implementing reception in the EU Member States and specifically Greece. The term “reception” is used to map the conditions under which the applicants have access to housing, food, clothing, health care, education for minors and access to employment. Even though the time frame of “reception” is not clearly defined in EU legislation, for the purpose of RESPOND programme we have chosen to follow the definition considering that reception starts as soon as the border of a given state has been crossed and an application for international protection has been made. In these terms and in our working understanding, reception refers to the liminal period between the arrival and application for asylum and the issuing of a decision on the asylum application.

This report is part of the fourth Work Package of RESPOND and focuses on refugee reception policies in the period 2011-2018 and on reception practices since 2015 in Greece. The definition and scope of “reception” in EU legislation serves as a common point of departure and a heuristic to grasp the various dimensions of “reception”. More specifically, Directive 2013/33/EU points out a number of “material conditions” of reception including “housing, food and clothing provided in kind, or as financial allowances or in vouchers, or a combination of the three, and a daily expenses allowance”. Additionally, issues of education and basic healthcare are defined in the Directive as issues that ought to be provided during the period of reception, and criteria for proper accommodation are formulated.

The main goal of this WP4 Greece report is to present and discuss the legislative measures and policies, the reception practices followed by state and non-state agencies and the experiences of asylum-seekers with regards to reception in Greece. Following the WP1, WP2 and WP3 reports that focused on the overview of the “Legal & Policy Framework of Migration Governance”, “Border Management and Migration Controls in Greece” and “Refugee Protection” respectively, this report will concentrate mostly on the implementation of Refugee Reception. The analysis of the implementation of Refugee Reception is conducted both through a review of published reports on reception and on the basis of the gathered empirical research evidence on the experiences, perceptions and actions of actors and asylum-seekers.

The political and social context of the period in question is determined by both the multilevel socioeconomic recession in Greece and the increased refugee arrivals. In spring 2015, as a result of the war (mainly in Syria) and of the overall adverse conditions prevailing in other countries, refugees mostly from Syria but also from Iraq, Afghanistan, Eritrea and Somalia, started to enter Greece in larger numbers. In 2015 alone, more than 850,000 migrants made the crossing to Greece in an attempt to make their way to other EU countries. The aforementioned years bore witness to significant developments regarding legislation on refugee reception in Greece. Some of the relevant laws that should be mentioned in this regard are Law 3907/2011, Law 4375/2016 that followed the EU-Turkey Statement of 18 March 2016 and Law 4540/2018 that amended the Greek legislation in accordance with the provisions of Directive 2013/33/EU on the standards required for the reception of applicants for international protection.

Generally speaking, the reception system in Greece consists of three different types of accommodation: a) accommodation in the Reception and Identification Centres established in the Northeastern Aegean islands (Hotspots) and in the Northeastern town of Fylakio, b) Temporary Accommodation Centres (camps) in mainland Greece and c) accommodation and housing in apartments and buildings in the urban space. According to figures of the former Ministry of Migration policy, as of 19 September 2018, 25,000 migrants were staying in apartments, approximately 23,000 to 25,000 in camps on the mainland and about 20,000 on the islands (Council of Europe, 2018). The vast majority of reception camps remain unsuitable even for short-term accommodation. Asylum-seekers and refugees as well as humanitarian organisations repeatedly report the inhuman living conditions in the reception and accommodation facilities in Greece. In its opinion issued in July 2016 after visiting 16 camps both in mainland and in the Northeastern Aegean islands, the Hellenic Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (KEELPNO) proposed the “complete closure of hospitality centres” (KEELPNO, 2016). The deaths of refugees, not only in the Hotspots but also in camps in the mainland (Infomobile, 2017), are the most alarming facts highlighting the aforementioned.

It should also be mentioned that there has been a shift in the Greek political context since the writing of the previous reports. The SYRIZA-led coalition government of 2015-2019 has been replaced by the right-wing ND government following the recent national elections of July 2019. The Ministry of Migration Policy, established in 2016, has been abolished as an independent ministry and transformed into a General Secretariat for Immigration Policy, Reception and Asylum belonging to the Ministry of Citizen Protection while in January 2020 it has been re-established under the name of the “Ministry of Migration and Asylum”. Additionally, a wide range of conservative measures on refugee issues have been – mostly – announced but also implemented. Examples of measures already taken include sweep operations in refugee squats in the centre of Athens and the transfer of refugees to camps located in remote mainland areas. More recently, Law 4636/2019 was adopted and will enter into force as of 01/01/2020. Even if these developments are not relevant for the 2011-2018 timeframe that this report focuses on, it is important they be mentioned as they corroborate and emphasise the temporary and fluid character of the investigated issues.

The report is divided into 5 sections, including introduction, methodology and conclusions. The third section presents the “Policies and Legal Regulations of Reception”. The section entitled “Practices of Reception” analyses the different types of accommodation and housing; the practices of early access to education and the labour market; the services and allowances provided; and the encounter with officials, civic actors and the receiving society. However, extended analysis has been provided particularly for the section of accommodation and housing, as the serious lack of capacity both in terms of space availability and in terms of services provided in the respective accommodation sites, has been reported. Thus on the base of the research implemented, it is considered that the accommodation system affects significant aspects of reception, such as the provision of psychosocial support, medical care, education and everyday living conditions for asylum seekers.

Methodology and Sources

The research methodology implemented for the needs of this report and the overall RESPOND programme combined diverse methods and data from different sources in order to provide comprehensive insights to regulations, policies, practices and experiences of reception in Greece. The section on regulations and policies is based on a document analysis of legislative and policy documents. Legislative documents comprise relevant acts of international, supranational and national law but also jurisdiction and authoritative administrative orders. The policy documents analysed comprise a number of position papers, reports by national and international organizations and NGOs and other forms of written political intervention in debates concerning the reception of refugees.

In addition, the report draws from semi-structured interviews with actors who are concerned with different dimensions of reception, specifically through meso level interviews. These interviews are also used to account for the institutional implementation of reception. They are complemented with public statistical data sources on reception. An integral part of this report is the critical analysis of reception policies and institutional practices of reception in the light of subjective experiences of reception. The meso level included 15 semi-structured interviews with executives and employees of the authorities, international organizations and NGOs. Additionally, a round-table discussion organised by the University of the Aegean working group in November 2018 provided crucial insights to the research.

Apart from the meso level interviews, the analysis on “Practices of Reception” is also based on 34 semi-structured micro level interviews with refugees from various countries of origin who live in Moria Camp and Athens and who arrived between 2011 and 2017, including a focus-group interview. The sample was approached using the snowball method. The interviewees were aware of the aims of this research and their anonymity and desire to speak off the record at certain moments of the interview were respected. Twelve (12) interviewees were of Afghan origin, of which 8 were raised in other countries such as Iran or Pakistan. Eight (8) came from Syria, including 3 Kurds. Additionally, there was a wide range of interviewees from other countries of origin such as Burundi (2 interviewees), Iraq (2 interviewees), Somalia (2 interviewees), Iran, Palestine, Cameroon, Congo, Eritrea, Guinea and Sudan. The proportion of men and women interviewees was: 75.75% males (25 in absolute numbers), 9.10% women (3 in absolute numbers), 15.15% couples (5 in absolute numbers) and 1 group interview (with both men and a woman). Most interviewees were aged 18 to 37, with some exceptions of older individuals. The list of the micro level interviewees with pseudonyms and personal information is provided in Table 6 in Appendices.

Data were analysed based on a qualitative content analysis approach which combines deductive and inductive elements. In the deductive method, categories of analysis were derived from the overarching research question about the match or mismatch of reception policies and practices across various levels of governance, as well as from the EU Reception Directive which distinguishes different dimensions of reception, such as allowances, accommodation, healthcare, access to education and legal counselling. In the inductive method, interviews with actors as well as with refugees were examined for additional themes and categories which have proved meaningful for a holistic understanding of the multilevel system of reception.

The qualitative analysis of the interview material was conducted using NVIVO software and organised on the basis of the major research issues of RESPOND (such as borders, protection, reception and integration). The NVIVO material regarding Reception was specifically used for the needs of this report. Despite the usefulness of NVIVO for the qualitative analysis of large numbers of interviews, it should be mentioned that in some cases the use of this kind of software has specific limitations. For example, in the present case, the exported nodes sometimes removed the personal history of interviewees. Thus, in some cases, it was necessary to re-incorporate information from the interviews' transcriptions – and not only from the nodes exported through NVIVO – in order to take into account the specific context of the interviewee's experiences, perceptions and practices.

Finally, as already mentioned, this report was written in a differentiated political context in Greece than the previous ones, due to the recent national elections in Greece and the veer to conservatism. As a result and considering recent announcements as well as legislation amendments made by the government, we expect significant changes regarding refugee reception. This highlights and corroborates the overall temporary and fluid character of the investigated issues, a methodological concern that should be mentioned.

Policies and Legal Regulations of Reception

This section presents and analyses the refugee reception legislative measures and policies in Greece, from 2011 to 2018. More specifically, the section provides a) an overview of the legal framework, b) the relevant reception and identification procedures as provided by the legislation, as well as c) the policies on several aspects of reception such as accommodation, health services, labour market and education. Last but not least, recent reforms that took place in 2019 are mentioned as they are considered to affect the relevant policies of reception in Greece.

An overview of the legal framework

The national legal framework on Refugee Reception in Greece, is interrelated with the European legislation. At the EU Level, the 2003 Reception Conditions Directive and its 2013 recast set out common minimum standards for the reception of applicants for international protection to ensure them “a dignified standard of living and comparable living conditions in all Member States”¹. In particular, the recast Reception Conditions Directive (Directive 2013/33/EU) deals with access to reception conditions for asylum-seekers while they wait for the examination of their claim. It ensures that applicants have access to housing, food, healthcare and employment, as well as medical and psychological care. It ensures that detention of applicants is always in line with fundamental rights and restricts the detention of vulnerable persons, in particular minors. Member States had to transpose the Directive and communicate their transposition measures by 20 July 2015².

At the national level, Presidential Decree (PD) 220/2007 (Reception Decree) transposed the 2003 Reception Conditions Directive into the Greek legislation and stated that the reception and accommodation of asylum-seekers fell within the competence of the services of the Ministry of Health and Social Solidarity. Until then, reception centres constituted an area of responsibility of the Ministry of Public Order. According to this PD, the Ministry of Health and Social Solidarity became responsible for the implementation of a full set of measures for the reception and accommodation of asylum-seekers, including material reception conditions³.

Despite these legal provisions and the structural framework for the organization and implementation of reception, the functioning of the reception system has been problematic, especially due to the lack of capacity of reception facilities. As a result, Greece has been

¹ Directive 2013/33/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 laying down standards for the reception of applicants for international protection (recast), available at: <https://bit.ly/36U0P3T>.

Council Directive 2003/9/EC of 27 January 2003 laying down minimum standards for the reception of asylum seekers, available at: <https://bit.ly/396O0Vd>.

² https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_16_270

³ Presidential Decree 220/2007, available at: <https://bit.ly/2RRYRwD> (in Greek).

repeatedly criticised and condemned over the years for its poor reception conditions and the shortcomings in asylum procedures⁴.

In line with the EU Action Plan, the Greek state issued Law 3907/2011⁵ which set up the establishment of three autonomous services under the Ministry of Citizen Protection; the Asylum Service, the Appeals Authority and the First Reception Service (FRS). Reception subsequently became the competence of the Ministry of Citizen Protection. The FRS became operational in 2013. Composed of a Central Service and Regional Services (First Reception Centres - FRCs - and Mobile Units), its objective was to process new arrivals through appropriate routing, assessment of needs and the provision of assistance, among others. The FRS was responsible for both establishing and running First Reception Centres (Dimitriadi et al., 2019).

However, the exceptional number of arrivals recorded in Greece in 2015, the introduction of the “Hotspot Approach” by the European Commission, as well as the signing of the EU-Turkey Statement in March 2016, brought about institutional changes both to the asylum procedures and to the structure of the reception system (Asylum Act, Law 4375/2016⁶). Greece created a Ministry of Migration Policy, detaching migration and asylum from the Ministry of Interior and Administrative Reform as well as transferring responsibility for reception from the Ministry of Labour, Social Insurance and Social Solidarity to the Ministry of Migration Policy. The Ministry of Migration Policy was composed of two Secretary Generals: one for Migration Policy and one for Reception and Identification.

Law 4375/2016 renamed the First Reception Service (FRS) as Reception and Identification Service (RIS). The RIS and the Accommodation Department of the Reception Directorate became responsible for the establishment, operation and supervision of “open temporary reception facilities” for persons who have requested international protection and of “open temporary accommodation structures” for persons who are undergoing a return, removal or readmission procedure. In this context, five “Reception and Identification Centres” (Hotspots) were created in the Eastern Aegean islands of Lesbos, Chios, Samos, Leros and Kos.

In 2018, Presidential Decree 220/2007 was repealed almost in its entirety after the adoption of Law 4540/2018 (Reception Act)⁷ and Law 4554/2018 on Guardianship⁸. Law

⁴ ECtHR, GC, MSS v. Greece and Belgium, Application no. 30696/09, 21/01/2011, available at: <https://bit.ly/36RPOzZ>

⁵ Law No. 3907/2011 on the establishment of an Asylum Service and a First Reception Service, transposition into Greek legislation of Directive 2008/115/EC "on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third country nationals" and other provisions, 26 January 2011, available at: <https://bit.ly/2Ur6awO>

⁶ Law 4375/2016 on the organisation and operation of the Asylum Service, the Appeals Authority, the Reception and Identification Service, the establishment of the General Secretariat for Reception, the transposition into Greek legislation of the provisions of Directive 2013/32/EC [Greece], 3 April 2016, available at: <https://bit.ly/393i7gp>

⁷ Law 4540/2018, Transposing Directive 2013/33/EU of the EU Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 into the Greek Legislation Establishing Standards for the Reception of Applicants for International Protection and Other Provisions, Amending Law 4251/2014 (GG A'80), Transposing the Directive 2014/66/EU of the EU Parliament and of the Council of 15 May 2014 on the Conditions of Entry and Residence of Third-Country Nationals in the Framework of an Intra-Corporate Transfer, Amending Asylum Procedures and Other Provisions [Greece], 22 May 2018, available at: <https://bit.ly/39064R1>

4540/2018 transposed the recast Reception Conditions Directive (2013/33/EU) into the Greek legislation, almost three years after the transposition deadline set by the Directive. Law 4540/2018 regulates the reception conditions for applicants of international protection, including freedom of movement for all applicants, as well as the possibility to restrict movement, the detention of categories of vulnerable persons, including minors, education for minors, material reception conditions and modalities for the reduction or withdrawal of reception conditions.

In addition, Law 4540/2018 reformed the authorities responsible for the reception of asylum-seekers⁹. The RIS and the Directorate for the Protection of Asylum-seekers within the Secretariat General of Migration Policy under the Ministry of Migration Policy (currently Ministry of Migration and Asylum), were appointed as the responsible authorities for reception. The Directorate General for Social Solidarity of the Ministry of Employment, Social Security and Social Solidarity was appointed as the responsible authority for protection, including the provision of reception conditions of unaccompanied and separated minors¹⁰.

Reception and identification procedures

As mentioned above, Law 3907/2011 established the FRS and set out first reception procedures for all third-country nationals who were arrested while entering the country irregularly. These procedures included: (a) verification of their identity and nationality, (b) registration, (c) medical examination and any necessary medical care and psychosocial support, (d) information about rights and obligations, in particular about the conditions under which one can be placed under international protection and (e) identifying those who belong to vulnerable groups so that the relevant procedures can be followed¹¹. Furthermore, the FRS was granted competence for the establishment and operation of open accommodation facilities for asylum-seekers and third-country nationals who have entered the country irregularly but belong to a vulnerable group.

Under Law 4375/2016, all third-country nationals and stateless persons who enter without complying with the legal formalities in the country shall be submitted to reception and identification procedures, which include:

- a) the registration of their personal data and the taking and registering of fingerprints for those who have reached the age of 14,
- b) the verification of their identity and nationality,
- c) their medical screening and the provision of any necessary care and psychosocial support,
- d) informing them about their rights and obligations, in particular the procedure for international protection or the procedure for entering a voluntary return program,

⁸ Law 4554/2018 (GG A' 130) on the Social Security and Pension Provision, Addressing Undeclared Work, Reinforcing of Protection of Workers, Guardianship for Unaccompanied Minors and Other Provisions [Greece], 18 July 2018, available at: <https://bit.ly/2ScUGKN>

⁹ Article 3(b) L 4540/2018

¹⁰ Article 22(3) L 4540/2018

¹¹ Article 7 L 3907/2011

e) attention to those belonging to vulnerable groups, in order to guide them to the appropriate, in each case, procedure and to provide them with specialised care and protection,

f) referring those who wish to apply for international protection to start the procedure for such an application,

g) referring those who do not apply for international protection or whose application is rejected while they remain in the RIC to the competent authorities for readmission, removal or return procedures¹².

Restriction on freedom of movement: Under Law 4375/2016, persons entering the Reception and Identification Centre shall be placed under a status of restriction of liberty. This decision is issued within three (3) days of their arrival and can be further extended by a maximum of 25 days from their entry into the Centre. Alternatively, the Manager of the Reception and Identification Centre at the border may, by a decision and particularly in the case of persons belonging to vulnerable groups, refer the third-country national or stateless person to a Reception and Identification Centre located inland or to other appropriate structures where the reception and identification procedure will be continued and completed.¹³

In practice, the imposition of a restriction on the freedom of movement is applied particularly on the five island Hotspots to persons falling under the EU-Turkey Statement, whose movement is systematically restricted within the island where they have arrived (known as “geographical restriction”). Geographical restriction is imposed both by the Police Authorities and the Asylum Service (AIDA, 2019a).

Law 4540/2018 reiterates the provisions regarding restriction of movement within a particular geographical area, imposed by a regulatory decision of the Director of the Asylum Service¹⁴. Finally, following an amendment in December 2018, Article 24 of Law 4540/2018 provides that applicants have the right to lodge an appeal before the Administrative Court against decisions imposing a restriction of movement. However, the remedy provided by this provision is not available in practice (AIDA, 2019a).

Provision of information: According to Law 4375/2016, the information unit of the Reception and Identification Centre shall inform third-country nationals or stateless persons of their rights and obligations as well as of the procedures for receiving international protection status and the procedures for voluntary repatriation¹⁵. According to Law 4540/2018, the competent authorities shall inform the applicant, within 15 days after the lodging of the application for international protection, of his or her rights and of the obligations with which he or she must comply relating to reception conditions, by providing an informative leaflet in a language that the applicant understands. This material must provide information on the existing reception conditions, including health care, as well as on the organizations that provide legal and psychological assistance to asylum-seekers¹⁶.

¹² Article 9 (1) L 4375/2016

¹³ Article 14 (2), (3) L 4375/2016

¹⁴ Article 7 (1) L 4540/2018

¹⁵ Article 14 (7)) L 4375/2016

¹⁶ Article 5 (1),(2) L 4540/2018

Access to actors: Asylum-seekers in reception facilities have the right to be in contact with relatives, legal advisors, representatives of UNHCR and other certified organizations. These shall have unlimited access to reception centres and other housing facilities in order to assist applicants. The Director of the Centre may extend access to other persons as well. Limitations to such access may be imposed only on grounds relating to the security of the premises and of the applicants¹⁷.

Assessment of vulnerability: The assessment of the vulnerability of persons entering without the legal formalities into the territory takes place within the framework of the Reception and Identification Procedure and is not connected to the assessment of the asylum application¹⁸. Under the reception and identification procedure, the Head of the RIC, acting on a proposal of the Head of the medical screening and psychosocial support unit, shall refer persons belonging to vulnerable groups to the competent social support and protection institutions¹⁹.

Reception conditions

According to the definition given by law, “reception conditions” means the full set of measures that the Greek state grants to third-country nationals or stateless persons who have applied for international protection (hereinafter the applicants), whereas “material reception conditions” means the reception conditions that include housing, food and clothing provided in kind or as financial allowances or in vouchers, or a combination of the three, and a daily expenses allowance²⁰.

Access to reception conditions:

Law 4540/2018 provides that the competent Reception Authority, in cooperation with the competent public bodies, international organizations or accredited social welfare organizations, as deemed appropriate, shall ensure that material reception conditions are available to applicants through the use of national, EU or other resources. Material reception conditions may be provided in kind or in the form of a financial allowance and shall provide an adequate standard of living for applicants, one which guarantees their subsistence and protects their physical and mental health with due regard to respect for human dignity²¹.

The law foresees that the provision of all or part of the material reception conditions depends on the asylum-seekers’ lack of employment or lack of sufficient resources to maintain an adequate standard of living²². The latter is examined in connection with the

¹⁷ Article 18(2)(b) L 4540/2018

¹⁸ Article 20 (2) L 4540/2018

¹⁹ Article 14 (8) L 4375/2016

²⁰ Article 2 L 4540/2018

²¹ Article 17 (1) L 4540/2018

²² Article 17 (3) L 4540/2018

financial criteria set for eligibility for the Social Solidarity Benefit (Κοινωνικό Επίδομα Αλληλεγγύης, ΚΕΑ)²³.

Reduction or Withdrawal from material reception conditions:

Reception conditions may be reduced or withdrawn where the applicant:

- Abandons the place of residence determined by the competent authority without informing it or, if requested, without permission; or
- Does not comply with reporting duties or with requests to provide information or to appear for personal interviews concerning the asylum procedure during a reasonable period laid down in national law; or
- Has lodged a Subsequent Application;
- Has concealed his or her resources and illegitimately takes advantage of material reception conditions; or
- Violates the house rules of the reception centre²⁴.

Moreover, material reception conditions may be reduced in cases where the competent reception authority can establish that the applicant, for no justifiable reason, has not lodged an application for international protection as soon as reasonably practicable after arriving on Greek territory²⁵. The law also provides that reception conditions can be reduced or withdrawn if it is established that the applicant has concealed his or her financial means²⁶. The RIS reaches a decision following an individualised assessment and taking into account the vulnerability of the applicant²⁷. In addition, it provides that the applicants against whom a decision reducing or withdrawing reception conditions is issued are entitled to appeal against such decision before administrative courts²⁸. However, the remedy provided by this provision is not available in practice.

Accommodation and housing:

According to Law 4540/2018, where housing is provided in kind, it should assume the following forms: premises used for the purpose of housing applicants during the examination of an application for international protection made at the border or in transit zones; accommodation centres under the management of public or private non-profit entities or international organizations; private houses, flats and hotels rented for the purposes of accommodation programs implemented by public or private non-profit entities or international organizations. In all cases, the provision of housing is under the supervision of the competent reception authority²⁹.

²³ Article 235 L 4389/2016

²⁴ Article 19 (1)) L 4540/2018

²⁵ Article 19 (2) L 4540/2018

²⁶ Article 19 (3) L 4540/2018

²⁷ Article 19 (5) L 4540/2018

²⁸ Article 24 (1) L 4540/2018

²⁹ Article 18(1) L 4540/2018

Access to health services:

According to national legislation, asylum-seekers are entitled to free of charge access to necessary health, pharmaceutical and hospital care, including necessary psychiatric care where required. Specifically, the previous relevant legislation (article 14 of the Presidential Decree 220/2007) provided that asylum-seekers who were uninsured and didn't have sufficient resources were entitled to free access to hospitals and medical care. This provision was abolished by Law 4540/2018³⁰. The legislation currently in force³¹ further settles the matter, providing that asylum-seekers have free access to public health structures and to nursing and health care, including the necessary treatment for illness and the necessary psychiatric care, if required, according to article 33 of Law 4368/2016. According to the provisions of Article 33 of Law 4368/2016 and the relevant ministerial decision, asylum-seekers belong to the "socially vulnerable groups" who have the right to access the public healthcare and medical system of the country (CoE, 2019).

Access to education:

According to Law 4540/2018, asylum-seeking children have access to the education system under similar conditions as Greek nationals, and facilitation is provided in case of incomplete documentation as long as no removal measure against them or their parents is actually enforced. Access to secondary education shall not be withheld for the sole reason that the child has reached the age of maturity³². Registration may not take longer than 3 months from the identification of the child³³. A Ministerial Decision issued in August 2016 established a programme of afternoon preparatory classes (Δομές Υποδοχής και Εκπαίδευσης Προσφύγων, DYEP) for all school-age children aged 4 to 15³⁴.

Access to the labour market:

Law 4375/2016 provides that applicants for international protection who have completed the procedure for lodging the application for international protection in accordance with the relevant provisions and are in possession of an "international protection applicant card" or "asylum-seeker's card" shall have access to salaried employment or to the provision of services or works³⁵. However, applicants who have not yet completed the full registration or lodged their application, i.e. applicants who are pre-registered, do not have access to the labour market (AIDA, 2018). Law 4540/2018 provides that the right of access to the labour market shall not be withdrawn during appeals procedures until such time as a negative decision on the appeal is notified³⁶.

³⁰ Article 30 (6) L 4540/2018

³¹ Article 17 L 4540/2018

³² Article 13 (1) L 4540/2018

³³ Article 13 (2) L 4540/2018

³⁴ Ministerial Decision 152360/ΓΔ4/2016, GG 3049/B/23-09-2016, available in Greek at: <http://bit.ly/2IbVKGp>.

³⁵ Article 71 L 4375/2016

³⁶ Article 15 (2) L 4540/2018

Furthermore, Law 4540/2018 provides that applicants can have access to vocational training programmes under the same conditions and prerequisites as foreseen for Greek nationals and that the conditions for the assessment of the skills of applicants who do not have the necessary documentation will be set by a Joint Ministerial Decision³⁷ which has not been issued yet.

Vulnerable persons:

Law 4540/2018 introduces the term “applicant with special reception needs” to define the vulnerable person who is in need of special procedural guarantees in order to benefit from the rights and comply with the obligations provided by this Act³⁸.

According to Article 20 (1) of the aforementioned law, when applying the provisions on reception conditions, competent authorities shall take into account the specific situation of vulnerable persons such as minors, unaccompanied or not, disabled people, elderly people, pregnant women, single parents with underaged children, persons with serious illnesses, persons with mental disorders and persons who have been subjected to torture, rape or other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence, victims of female genital mutilation and victims of human trafficking.

Importantly, Law 4540/2018 led to modifications regarding the competent authorities for the reception of unaccompanied and separated children. The Directorate-General for Social Solidarity of the Ministry of Labour, Social Security and Social Solidarity has been appointed as the responsible authority for the protection, including reception, of unaccompanied and separated children,³⁹ and the National Centre for Social Solidarity (EKKA) under the Ministry of Labour receives and further processes referrals for accommodation of unaccompanied and separated children.

Recent Reforms

In October 2019, a new bill which consolidates the rules on qualification, reception and the asylum procedure in a single legislative instrument was submitted to the Greek Parliament by the Ministry of Citizen Protection. Law 4636/2019⁴⁰ was published on 01.11.2019 and came into force on 01.01.2020. The new legislative reform introduces significant changes to asylum procedures, the rights and obligations of asylum-seekers, reception and detention, as well as the economic, social and cultural rights of asylum-seekers (Amnesty International, 2019). The most remarkable changes regarding conditions of reception are the following:

³⁷ Article 16 L 4540/2018

³⁸ Article 2 L 4540/2018

³⁹ Article 22 (3) L 4540/2018

⁴⁰ Law 4636/2019, regarding international protection and other provisions, 1 November 2019, available in Greek at: <https://collab.lawspot.gr/sites/default/files/mashup/feka/2019/fek-169-2019.pdf>

- Article 51 (2): provides the reduction of material conditions of reception for asylum-seeking children who don't enrol in public schools and for the adult members of his/her family,
- Article 53 (1): provides that the applicants for international protection have access to employment only 6 months after the completion of the submission of the application for international protection,
- Article 55 (2): provides that access to public health facilities, the labour market and social security will be granted through K.Y.P.A. (Foreigner Health Cards), issued by the Asylum Service.

The new legislative reform triggered the reaction of many actors, such as UNHCR, the Ombudsman, the National Commission for Human Rights and non-governmental organizations, who expressed their concern that the new law brings about several restrictions on individual rights and procedural guarantees in the Greek asylum system (AIDA, 2019a).

Table 1. Reception legislation

European Legislation	National Legislation
<p>Directive 2013/33/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 laying down standards for the reception of applicants for international protection (recast)</p> <p>Council Directive 2003/9/EC of 27 January 2003 laying down minimum standards for the reception of asylum-seekers No longer in force, Date of end of validity: 20/07/2015</p>	<p>Law 4636/2019, regarding international protection and other provisions Gazette 169/1-09-2019</p> <p>Law 4540/2018, Transposing Directive 2013/33/EU of the EU Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 into the Greek Legislation Establishing Standards for the Reception of Applicants for International Protection and Other Provisions Gazette 91/A/22-5-2018</p> <p>Law 4554/2018 on the Social Security and Pension Provision, Addressing Undeclared Work, Reinforcing of Protection of Workers, Guardianship for Unaccompanied Minors and Other Provisions Gazette A' 130/18.7.2018</p> <p>Law 4375/2016 on the organization and operation of the Asylum Service, the Appeals Authority, the Reception and Identification Service, the establishment of the General Secretariat for Reception, the transposition into Greek legislation of the provisions of Directive 2013/32/EC Gazette 51/A/3-4-2016</p> <p>Law 3907/2011 on the establishment of an Asylum Service and a First Reception Service, transposition into Greek legislation of Directive 2008/115/EC "on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third country nationals" and other provisions. Gazette 7/A/26-01-2011</p> <p>Presidential Decree (P.D.) 220/2007 on the transposition into the Greek legislation of Council Directive 2003/9/EC from January 27, 2003 laying down minimum standards for the reception of asylum-seekers Gazette 251/A/13-11-2007 (In force only the article 19 (1))</p>

Practices of Reception

This section of the report focuses on practices of reception as they emerged from the research conducted for the needs of the RESPOND programme. The analysis is based on extracts from the meso and micro level semi-structured interviews, combined with sources such as reports from actors and institutions, in order to provide crucial insights on aspects of the implementation of refugee reception in Greece. Different dimensions of reception are analysed, such as accommodation and housing, early access to education and the labour market and different types of services and allowances. Additionally, encounters with officials, civil society actors and the receiving society are presented, as well as experiences of “welcome” culture, negative attitudes and racist practices against refugees in Greece as they emerged from the research. Moreover, special attention is given to dimensions of gender dynamics and vulnerable groups.

1. Accommodation and Housing

In this part of the report, the accommodation and housing system for asylum-seekers in Greece is presented and analysed by drawing from both a wide range of reports by actors and from the experiences and perceptions of the interviewees themselves. Due to the fact that housing is also a crucial theme in integration policies and practices (and is therefore analysed separately in the WP5 Integration Report of the RESPOND Programme), in this WP4 Reception report, housing mainly refers to temporary accommodation while the asylum application is processed.

The official accommodation system in Greece for asylum-seekers is based on the Reception and Identification Centres established in the Northeastern Aegean islands (Hotspots) and in the northeastern town of Fylakio, on the Temporary Accommodation Centres (camps) in mainland Greece as well as on the accommodation and housing programs in the urban space. As of 19 September 2018, 25,000 migrants were staying in apartments, approximately 23,000 to 25,000 in camps on the mainland, and about 20,000 on the islands (Council of Europe, 2018; Ministry of Migration Policy, 2018). Additionally, a number of asylum-seekers live informally in the large Greek cities and especially in Athens, in self-rented apartments and squats.

According to Law 4540/2018 (art. 3), the authorities responsible for the reception of asylum-seekers are the Reception and Identification Service (RIS) and the Directorate for the Protection of Asylum-seekers under the Ministry of Migration and Asylum. Additionally, accommodation in urban centres is implemented by UNHCR under the scheme “Emergency Support to Integration and Accommodation programme - ESTIA” by receiving and processing relevant referrals for vulnerable asylum-seekers eligible to be hosted under the scheme. The National Centre for Social Solidarity (EKKA) of the Ministry for Labour, Social Security and Social Solidarity is appointed as the responsible authority for protection, including the provision of reception conditions to unaccompanied and separated children.

Figure 1. Map of the RICs and Camps in Greece, until September 2018. Source: UNHCR (2018) Site Profiles August - September 2018. [online] Available at: <https://bit.ly/2PyOodH> [Accessed 25 November 2019].

The reception conditions at these different types of accommodation vary from place to place and from time to time. According to RSA-PRO ASYL, these different types reveal a patchwork approach to addressing the serious issues that exist in the reception system for refugees and asylum-seekers rather than a well-constructed mechanism (RSA-PRO ASYL, 2019, p. 1). The response of the Greek authorities and, more specifically, of the country's reception system still remain in the mindset of an emergency mode. The reception system is characterised by the absence of long-term planned solutions and its financing is still based on EU emergency assistance, thus reducing the long-term effectiveness of relevant programs (RSA-PRO ASYL, 2019, p. 2). The Greek reception system has been long criticised as inadequate, and the failure of national authorities to provide asylum-seekers with adequate living conditions has been broadly reported.

1.1 Accommodation in Reception and Identification Centres

The official Reception and Identification Centers (RICs) established in Greece operate in the Evros region at Northern Greece and in the Northeastern Aegean islands (known as “Hotspots”). In this section, the main reception practices relevant to the RICs are presented, as well as the crucial implementation challenges that characterize the function of these structures until today.

Accommodation in the Reception and Identification Centre at Fylakio, Evros

The Reception and Identification Centre at Fylakio, Evros, began its operation in March 2013. It is located outside Fylakio, a little village of about 500 inhabitants in Northern Evros, close to the land border with Turkey and Bulgaria, and it is situated immediately next to the Detention Centre of Fylakio. Although it is called a “reception” centre, those accommodated there are not allowed to leave without permission and are, according to the law, subjected to a “restriction of their freedom”, therefore under a regime of detention (ECRE-AIDA, 2015). In 2014, the RIC in Fylakio received third-country nationals arrested by the Hellenic Police Directorate of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, Evros, Komotini and Samothraki Island for irregularly crossing the border or irregularly residing on the territory. However, in 2013, the centre also took in persons who were apprehended in other Greek islands so as to alleviate the pressure placed on the latter by the large number of arrivals and the lack of reception capacity (ECRE-AIDA, 2015).

In the first half of 2018, land arrivals in Greece's Northeastern Evros region increased and the RIC of Fylakio rapidly became overcrowded; this resulted in the detention of thousands of people, including children, in police stations and pre-removal centres pending their transfer to the RIC (Council of Europe, 2018). A Human Rights Watch report found that thousands of migrants, including asylum-seekers, had been subject to appalling reception conditions, with at-risk groups – including pregnant women and new mothers – lacking necessary protection, especially health care, and that the RIC of Fylakio “failed to meet such basic standards as having toilets and locking doors” (HRW, 2018).

Accommodation in the Reception and Identification Centres of the Northeastern Aegean islands

The Reception and Identification Centres established in the Northeastern Aegean islands (Hotspots) constitute both Identification Centres (where the first registration of the newly arrived takes place) but also Reception Centres, where (following the EU-Turkey Statement and the implementation of geographical restriction) asylum-seekers may reside for a long period of time. We have already elaborated on the protection issues emerging from the Hotspot system (Leivaditi et al., 2020), based on our understanding of refugee protection not merely as institutional protection but also as the provision of full and equal respect for human rights and coverage of basic human needs, survival and physical security. In this report, we draw from the field research conducted in order to highlight serious issues regarding reception and living conditions at the RICs.

The situation on the islands has been widely documented and remains extremely alarming. It would be no exaggeration to claim that prevailing reception conditions are

inhuman, in particular in the Hotspot facilities. The imposition of geographical restriction on the islands since the launch of the EU-Turkey Statement has led to significant overcrowding in the reception facilities on the islands. Overcrowding has been more severe at times throughout the year, particularly in Lesvos and Samos. This situation severely affects the availability of shelter, sanitary facilities, food and medical resources for inhabitants and poses significant protection risks, as people living there are exposed to the weather conditions, food and water supply is reportedly insufficient, sanitation is poor and security is highly problematic (AIDA, 2019a). The living conditions prevailing in the RICs are also the cause of physical and mental health issues.

Table 2. Accommodation in the RICs at the Northeastern Aegean islands: 31 December 2018.

Source: <https://bit.ly/36nkMjw>

Island	RIC	
	Nominal capacity	Occupancy
Lesvos	3100	5010
Chios	1014	1252
Samos	648	3723
Leros	860	936
Kos	816	762
Total	6438	11683

According to more recent data, on 6 June 2019 there were 16,108 refugees, asylum-seekers and migrants stranded on the Greek islands of Samos, Chios, Lesvos, Leros and Kos. Of those, 12,628 lived in the Hotspots, although these centres have the capacity to accommodate 6,438 (RSA-PRO ASYL, 2019:1).

The example of Moria Hotspot

Most interviews conducted with refugees in Lesvos make reference to the direct transfer from the boat and the beach of arrival to the Moria Hotspot since 2016. The same procedure applies to refugees arriving in the other Eastern Aegean islands where Hotspots are established, as some interviewees who arrived at Chios and Kos island reveal. In the case of Lesvos, refugees are transferred by bus from the beach to Moria Hotspot, rarely having received any prior information. The transfer is usually conducted with UNHCR buses, especially for arrivals at the north of Lesvos island. After their registration in Moria Hotspot, accommodation should be provided to the newly arrived, a service usually coordinated by NGO EuroRelief.

“- Moria, we didn't expect Moria actually. It's like a scene, a movie scene that you are shocked.”

- You arrive, they take the fingerprints to give you the identity, paper police and you are out.
- And then where did you go?
- The is a NGO which is called EuroRelief, those who are responsible for housing, accommodation, and they took us to the camp, to one of the tents after registration, we followed them, they gave us a tent and we started living there” (Kingslot).

There is a huge amount of reports from a wide range of actors revealing the inhuman living conditions in Moria Hotspot. Additionally, all the interviewees who experienced reception conditions in Moria reveal the inadequacy of the measures.

“- Let's talk about Moria. Moria is a bad place. You can go there, and you'll see. There aren't many things to say about Moria. [...] There are no words to talk about Moria. [...] Everything. Even the food, even the water, there are people sleeping on the floor, and in tents and the weather is cold, so, so bad” (Jack).

One of the first concerns is the overcrowding that prevails: despite the fact that the site has an official capacity of approximately 3,100, it is currently home to 16,753 (end of November 2019). This has gradually led to the creation of an informal camp in the surrounding olive grove known as “The Jungle” or “Olive Grove”. In this area, refugees live in unheated tents (also provided by EuroRelief), on mattresses or blankets on the ground, without adequate infrastructure.

“-First, when I arrived, I think what happened to me, so different. So when I came in Europe that I will like that life, that I will get that life, but when I came to Lesvos, first, when we arrived and they would ask us where are we from, and give us police papers just like that, they took everything and after that they gave us a little tent for three persons. Outside of camp, the camp was full.

-They gave us a little tent in a tree, you can't even stand up when you are inside, it's so short, it's only for vacation. [...] We still live there but we built a big tent. [...] Yes, outside. All Somalians they live outside. [...] All Somalians, except of children and female - they live inside, but others outside.

-And heating? Do you have heating?

-No, they didn't give us, they gave us a jacket. But they didn't give us...

-Is there electricity?

-Electricity, yes, just all we did it.

-DIY, by yourself.

-Yes, by ourselves. We bought everything, we tell from inside from the camp to outside, is a long...” (Aynla).

As revealed from the words of Aynla and from our field observations, the facilities provided inside Moria Hotspot are insufficient for the large number of people. For example, it has been reported that washing and hygiene facilities are very limited, there is limited access to running water, there is no hot water in the bathrooms and no electricity in the Olive Grove. Considering also the lack of cleanliness, both in the main camp and in the Olive Grove, the overall conditions are unsanitary.

“Moria is a very big problem. Very, very big problem, because I remained there for six months. There is no warm water, ladies have to take bath with cold water. Now they have separated the bathrooms of the ladies and gents, but when I was there,

they were combined. They used combined bathrooms. No cleaning. There are too many germs. I will give an example, one bathroom is being used by 600 people. Especially for females, it was common for women to have vaginal problems. They don't get clothes, etc. Then the new arrivals, one family gets just one blanket. In this cold weather. They have small children. How should they manage in cold?" (Fatima).

"First, when you are refugee, you need help. And they don't give you a good help. First meal is not good, it's not good and it's more people, even you can't, sometimes you can't get the meal and the second, the conditions, you see always is raining and our house is a tent and always water can get inside, and they see and always stay there in olive, and they say yes, we will help you, even if they don't give you something, and the other thing is that your decision will take long time. [...] The condition in Moria is not good. The life in Moria, living in Moria is not good" (Aynla).

Regarding hygiene and sanitation infrastructures, the ratio of washing facilities (toilets, showers, taps, etc.) to the population is often disproportionate. Water service is often interrupted, while lack of hot water has been repeatedly reported. Maintenance works are also undertaken by NGOs and not the state (GNCHR, 2016). In the Moria Hotspot, hygiene facilities (toilets, showers) are absolutely inadequate and the "lack of cleaning" of common spaces and toilets can pose a serious threat to public health.

"How can almost 10,000 (these days 17,000)... and the bathroom in the shower are little. For 1,000 people 9 toilets, for the woman 3 bathrooms, 9 toilets, for men 3 bathrooms. For the last 3 months I make shower every morning with cold water" (Group Interview, Community leader of Pakistan).

"Today I went in 6 o'clock in the morning I want you to go to the bathroom and there. No water from 9 to 10 o'clock. We don't have water, I took a bottle of water and waited inside. Is that good for the people? We are not animals!" (Group Interview, Community leader of Arabs).

In the context of the aforementioned inhuman conditions, fights between asylum-seekers of different groups or ethnicities have been reported as common, including the injury of people caused by the violent attacks. As an interviewee mentioned "Moria produces violence instead of protection, and the system does not undertake the responsibility".

"And the paradox is that, here, instead of people being protected we see people being retraumatised, there are physical and mental health problems that are created or aggravated here, there is rape and violence here and no one undertakes the protection of these people, a protection they truly need. Moria produces violence and traumatising experiences, and the system will not assume the responsibility" (Representative of Lesbos Solidarity NGO in Moria Hotspot).

There have been deaths of refugees due to these conditions since 2017, particularly during the days of snow in the winter of 2017 when people tried to keep warm by lighting fires, sometimes inside the tents.

"Instead of things getting better, it is getting worse and worse. People still live in tents, still complaining about the shower place, to take a shower, bathroom, food

and asylum. Things that we used to complain about 3 years ago. Like in 2016. Everything is the same. In 2016 and 2017 seven people died in winter. There was a small explosion first of all in a family tent, the grandmother died and 1 kid died, because it was so cold it was freezing and snowing, people started to light fires in the tents but they didn't know that it took all the oxygen and they died. 7 people died in 2016. And they did nothing" (Kingslot).

The absence of winterization plans for Hotspots on the Greek islands has been a persistent problem since 2016 and the implementation of EU-Turkey Statement. This has become a major issue of concern not only among humanitarian organizations but also for the Greek government and the European Commission (RSA-PRO ASYL, 2019, p. 10). The more recent event of another fire in which a woman burned to death in Moria Hotspot, on Sunday 29 September 2019, raises serious concerns. The woman's death was the third in the last two months (since September 2019). An Afghan teenager was killed in a fight in August and a five-year-old boy was run over by a truck while playing in a cardboard box outside the camp in September.

Gender-based experiences in Moria Hotspot

The inadequate living conditions in the reception centres in Greece have a serious impact on the safety and overall well-being of the most vulnerable groups, such as LGBTQ persons as well as women and their children. Women who reside in the reception centres in Greece systematically report being victims of sexual violence. The most common forms of such violence include inappropriate behaviour, sexual harassment, attempted sexual attacks as well as rape (also against children). One of the female research participants who was willing to discuss gender-based experiences with us, Fatima from Afghanistan, noted:

"In Moria, I was there for 6 months, I couldn't move around [...] because the people, the refugees are drinking alcohol and they are not in their senses, there is fighting, especially in Moria, in the grove garden... Yes, the conditions are too [...] at that part, because there is no police and no doctors in that part. Even in the jungle there were men coming from there and they were discussing about a woman, that she was crying, that in olive grove her 7 years old son has been raped" (Fatima).

"- Which people think that they are the most vulnerable inside Moria if you can tell me?

- Women, I can say they are the most vulnerable because, if you see even the toilet we are using, it's not appropriate for women [...] Because I've heard a lot of stories saying that they are trying not to use very often the toilets because they are afraid. [...] And the second risk for me is rape, because there is a woman, also she has been raped but she's quiet, that's why I say most of the things depend on the culture. Like most of the African women, if she gets raped, she will keep it secret because she will keep up a lonely life. Because man will know that this woman was being raped it will be like that, someone's doesn't have value in your community don't say me for me is a person like that needs big support" (Penen).

"I was in Moria, trying to understand why there was a woman sleeping outside First Reception, and she told me her child had been taken by someone who tried to rape it, and she couldn't go back to the place so she slept there. I went to the police and

the officer in charge said yes, well, we know that, we know what has happened, it's not the first time, the first time we have the attempted rape of a child, it wasn't the first time. And I said OK, so what now, and he said that, because there have been no reports by the parents, we have done nothing" (Volunteer in an NGO at Moria Hotspot).

The extremely insecure conditions of living for women and their vulnerable children, particularly in the overcrowded Hotspot of Moria, were continuously highlighted by a lot of interviewees. These cases of abuses and rapes have been also systematically mentioned by a wide range of actors. For example Médecins Sans Frontières (MSF), has reported that every week, women and children who have been raped come to its clinic in Moria Hotspot and that in most cases, migrants do not complain for fear of reprisals (European Parliament, 2018a).

Furthermore, due to protection shortcomings and capacity shortages it is worth noting that single women and female heads of families, as well as their children, are often placed in tents with unknown men. As provided through police orders to ensure the protection and safety of women and children, there are separate sections for children and families in Moria. However, there is not enough space to accommodate all women and children in the centre and, as a result, unaccompanied children and families also reside in the common areas of Moria.

"Moria is a very big problem. Very, very big problem, because I remained there for 6 months. There is no warm water, ladies have to take bath with cold water. They used combined bathrooms. Not cleaning. There are too many germs. I will give an example, one bathroom is being used by 600 people. Especially for females, it was common for women to have vaginal problems" (Fatima).

Additionally, reports have been made about pregnant women sleeping in tents with no mattresses, mothers being returned to the RIC with their new-born babies and individuals returned to the RIC immediately after release from hospital following surgery (Council of Europe, 2018). Women with disabilities face additional barriers: the toilets and showers are far from their shelter, over rough terrain, and are not accessible for people with disabilities. Aid workers handling cases of sexual and gender-based violence affirm protection systems are virtually non-existent, leaving women and girls exposed to a high risk; the situation is further aggravated by overcrowding.

"You are keeping the refugees in Moria and at the summertime an African lady had to give birth in a tent, an Afghan man's wife and small kid had to die from heart issues inside the camp" (Thanasis – Mah).

In reception centres all over Greece, LGBTQ persons as well as women and children often avoid leaving their tents, especially after dark, while bathrooms and latrines become no-go zones for them. It is very common for adult women to ask NGOs for diapers, so that they will not have to go alone to the toilets at night out of fear of being assaulted.

The community leader of women from Afghanistan reported the following during a group interview conducted with all the community leaders of the site:

“The situation in Moria is not good. The first problem is when a woman goes to the food line, it’s too long and you leave your family for one or two hours. Then they push each other, elder women must stay in the line. The biggest problem is the hygiene, we get infections, we can’t eat properly, then we cannot feed our children properly. We can’t go anywhere, and we are getting raped” (Female community leader of women from Afghanistan, Group Interview).

There is also a lack of services focusing on the empowerment and improvement of safety conditions for women, such as sufficient SGBV case management and the involvement of female personnel in all stages of the reception and asylum procedures, conducting vulnerability assessments. Furthermore, during our research we were also informed that, due to several bureaucratic obstacles, there is a lack of awareness on response procedures and service providers, as well as a serious shortage of female interpreters and staff when reporting incidents.

Recent research conducted by Human Rights Watch in Moria Camp reported that women and girls meeting current vulnerability criteria said they had not been screened for vulnerability or identified as vulnerable for months, including survivors of gender-based violence, pregnant women, new mothers, women with disabilities and women alone with children under 18. This is linked, among others, to staff resignations and shortages affecting KEELPNO since late 2018, causing lengthy delays in the identification of vulnerable individuals and a subsequent lagging behind in providing any additional support.

1.2 Accommodation in Camps

A total of 29 camps (IOM, 2019), most of which were created in 2016 as temporary accommodation facilities in order to address urgent reception needs on the mainland following the imposition of border restrictions, are still in use (October 2019). Law 4375/2016 and Joint Ministerial Decisions provide for the establishment of open Temporary Reception Facilities for Asylum-seekers (*Δομές Προσωρινής Υποδοχής Αιτούντων Διεθνή Προστασία*), as well as open Temporary Accommodation Facilities (*Δομές Προσωρινής Φιλοξενίας*) for persons subject to return procedures or whose return has been suspended. Nevertheless, “most temporary accommodation centres and emergency facilities operate without a prior Ministerial Decision and the requisite legal basis. [...] Due to this, the responsible authorities and referral pathways for placement in these camps remains unclear” (AIDA, 2018).

According to more recent data provided by IOM and the programme “Improving the Greek Reception System through Site Management Support and Targeted Interventions in Long-Term Accommodation Sites”, the actors responsible for Camp Management are, in some cases, the RIS and, in other, the Ministry of Defence; as for Site Management Support, the Arbeiter-Samariter-Bund (ASB), the Danish Refugee Council (DRC) and the International Organization for Migration (IOM) (IOM, 2019). For a list of the camps in the mainland and on the islands, see Tables 4 and 5 in the Annex, and for statistics on gender and nationalities of asylum seekers staying in camps see figures 5 and 6.

Figure 2. Actors responsible for Camp Management and Site Management Support (IOM, 2019).

Camp Management	Actor(s)	
		RIS: 8 Sites - MoD: 6 Sites - MoD & RiS: 13 Sites Municipality of Andravida, Kyllini in: 1 Site Perfecture of Central Greece: 1 Site No Representative: 2 Sites
		Types of Sites 27 LTAS, 1 Site as 9 Hotels, 1 Transit Site
Site Management Support	Actor(s)	
	ASB, DRC, IOM	
	Coordination meetings	24 Sites / 82.76%
	Community meetings	25 Sites / 86.21%
	Community feedback mechanism	25 Sites / 86.21%

Between the RICs and the Camps in the mainland, as well as between the different accommodation Camps in Greece, significant differences have been reported regarding the reception conditions. In general, these disparities consolidate inequalities in housing conditions in the accommodation centres. Conditions remain poor in a number of facilities on the mainland, as overcrowding, lack of or insufficient provision of services, violence, lack of security and lack of requisite legal base are reported. Despite the fact that the capacity of mainland camps increased in 2018, due inter alia to the increase of arrivals through the land borders in 2018, overcrowding occurred and even worsened in a number of mainland camps in 2018 (AIDA, 2018). As reported by UNHCR at the end of 2018, “the Government has increased the capacity in mainland sites and is preparing additional ones. [...] Nevertheless, the shortage of accommodation country-wide is increasingly leading to the overcrowding of many mainland camps, creating tension and increasing protection risks for the residents”

(UNHCR, 2018c). Limited services, including a low number of doctors and cultural mediators, as well as violence incidents and lack of security are also reported.

One of the most important negative characteristics of the camps in mainland Greece is the fact that they are usually established in remote areas, outside the urban environment, at a significant distance from the closest cities and without adequate transportation, resulting in the spatial segregation of the asylum-seekers residing there. This also affects their employment opportunities, as they have to travel for many hours to reach their workplace if they are employed.

The example of the camps on Lesbos island

As reported in the interviews, the most vulnerable residents of Moria Hotspot should be transferred to more adequate accommodation facilities, even to camps in Lesbos, or to apartments in Lesbos or in the mainland. As already mentioned in the 3rd report on “Protection”, refugees call the vulnerability procedure “Yes/No Doctor”, and the result of this procedure determines the next accommodation steps that these vulnerable asylum-seekers should follow (Leivaditi et al., 2020).

“About two months I was there in Moria, then I was waiting about 1 and 1/2 months and then I applied for a house. Then they told me that they will take me to Athens and will provide you the house so you will be there and when I was applying for the house I was waiting about 1 and 1/2 months. Then they told me they will take me to Athens and they will provide the house, but I was inside the Moria's camp about 2 months” (Abdul).

According to interviewees who had stayed in different facilities in Lesbos, living conditions in the accommodation camps of the island are better than those in Moria Hotspot.

“We should tell the truth. Inside the Hotspot there wasn't life. With so many people. But the other 2 camps in Lesbos weren't comparable with Moria, regarding sleeping, food, papers, everything. As they told us, life in these 2 camps was much better than Moria” (Medin & Farus).

-So, tell me a bit about the conditions in the camp.

-It is better now, it is safer, children play with other children and when the Christmas holidays are over, they will go to school in Mytilene.

-A public school or an NGO?

-Public school.

-Are there only families staying at the camp?

-Yes.

-Do you live alone in a container or are there more families

-Yes, alone

-And what services do they provide there?

-It is much better than Moria, much much better, regarding food and everything.

-Is there a queue for food or do they bring it to you at home?

-Apart from the fact that they bring it to us, there is also a kitchen where anyone can go and cook whatever we want.

-There is a common kitchen where people can cook?

-Yes, two big kitchens.

-So, how is your everyday life in the camp?

-Well, the most important thing is that the children are well here, and we know, when they go out, that they are safe, this is the important thing. And the police at the entrance of the camp will never let a child leave on its own, this is the most important thing (Nam & Mohammad).

According to our interlocutors the accommodation camps in Lesvos island, even though they face capacity shortages and in some cases protection shortcomings, they ensure the basic standards of living conditions. This fact, of course, does not reverse the aforementioned problematic situation of reception camps in Greece.

The example of the camps in mainland Greece

If comparing Moria Hotspot to the camps in Lesvos reveals the better conditions prevailing in the camps, a closer look at reception conditions in camps in mainland Greece reveals once again serious shortcomings, as presented in the introduction of this section. A number of serious concerns was revealed by interviewees who experienced reception conditions in mainland camps.

-How was the situation in Oinofyta, how many days did you stay there?

-About 40 days.

-Ok, it wasn't very well, because they always have many Arab-speaking refugees, they are very noisy, they break things, and there might be a lot of people, very few toilets, we cannot take a bath. It wasn't a good situation as we have in the house. And it the camp people receive less money than we receive now. Because, there, they cook, and no one would eat the food because it is not prepared well, so we would go and buy food with our money. We would often go hungry, we could not buy anything, there are no shops inside the camp, and we would stay without food all night long. There was a lot of trouble from the Arab-speaking refugees who had arrived before our family. When they were going to take us to apartments they complained, because they had arrived before us and we were taken to apartments before them. My wife was pregnant, that is why! Those who arrived by sea to the islands made a lot of trouble and we arrived last. There were 70-80 families inside the camp, they made a lot of trouble" (Hafiz & Banek).

-How was the situation in the camps at Oinofyta and Skaramaga?

-It was not good at all, first of all there are a lot of people, a lot of noise, and the children could not sleep with all the music, the noise, the shouting, the food was like rubber, they would bring it every day and every day the people took it back and asked 'would you eat this'? (Mohsin & Lima).

"When I was in Elaionas camp, I was feeling poor and uncomfortable because people were drinking and I was just wasting time and I said why am I wasting my time, I should find a job, and then I found a job" (Abdul).

Similar concerns emerge from the meso-level interviews:

"I was talking to a girl in Malakasa in order to process a transfer case, I had already spoken to the person she had told me. That person said he/she had been placed in a tent along with another five people, I suppose it was a large group, what can I

say. Four of them got up and left straight away. She said there was a rug and a thin mat on top, nothing else. As the girl who works at Malakasa explained, you gradually ascend levels there. At the beginning you get a tent, there are many people, then you might go to the next level which is a container or a Rab Hole. This is what camps offer, it is a camp for adults, they are transferred to camps. Especially away from city centres I think the situation is very difficult, there is only one way, I must go to the centre. And, in the centre, there are many dangers and temptations. Finding help there is difficult, you get lost, the situation is more chaotic. Getting help, etc., finding a home as well is very difficult. Once you leave the camp where the state has sent you, you lose the money you are entitled to, the UNHCR allowance. So, you either stay in the tent or lose your allowance. And if you stay in the tent you must wait in the tent. And for how long, what can you do in Malakasa? (Employee in NGO Praxis)".

Another serious issue reported often by the interviewees is the isolation of the mainland camps and, more specifically, the long distances between the camps and the closest cities, as well as the lack of frequent and adequate public transportation.

"We went to Malakasa. It is good there, it is good. Yes, but it is a bit far, there is only a train. No buses, just the train" (Ramon).

The isolation of several accommodation camps established in remote areas, has a serious impact on the everyday lives of asylum seekers in Greece. It has been usually reported that due to their stay in the spatially segregated camps, their everyday mobilities, their employment opportunities and their further adaptation with the host community are hampered.

Last but not least, it should be noted that camps are not per se suitable for long-term accommodation, as camps can have significant negative impacts over the longer term for all concerned. "Living in camps can engender dependency and weaken the ability of refugees to manage their own lives, which perpetuates the trauma of displacement and creates barriers to solutions, whatever form they take" (UNHCR, 2014:4). According to a 2016 report of the National Commission for Human Rights, housing conditions for refugees and migrants in the camps range from problematic to completely inadequate (NCHR, 2016). In its Resolution 2118 (2016) of 22 June 2016, the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe also expressed concern at living conditions in the reception centres on the mainland, which were described as falling far below acceptable standards (CoE, 2017).

1.3 Accommodation in apartments ("Emergency Support to Integration and Accommodation programme - ESTIA")

Apart from the Hotspots and the camps, accommodation in Greece is also provided through apartments in cities through the UNHCR accommodation scheme "Emergency Support to Integration and Accommodation programme - ESTIA", funded by the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund of the European Union. ESTIA started implementing a relocation scheme ("Accommodation for Relocation") and today it provides accommodation

in apartments in the urban space and cash assistance to asylum-seekers that meet specific vulnerability criteria, as well as to applicants for family reunification. Accommodation for asylum-seekers and recognised refugees is provided in 14 cities in the mainland and 7 islands. Over half (55%) of the accommodation places are in Athens, 38% in the rest of the mainland and 7% on the islands.

As of the end of October 2019, UNHCR is implementing the accommodation scheme through 23 partnerships with 12 national and international NGOs and 11 municipalities. In total, partners managed by UNHCR provided 100% of the accommodation places in Greece. UNHCR's accommodation partners are NGOs Praksis, Nostos, Catholic Relief Services (CRS), Iliaktida, Solidarity Now, Arsis, Intersos, Omnes, Perichoresis, and the municipalities of Athens (ADDMA), Thessaloniki (MUNTHESS), Trikala (E-TRIKALA), Livadia (KEDHL), Larissa (DIKEL), Nea Philadelphia - Nea Chalkidona (KEDFX), Karditsa (ANKA), Tripoli (PARNONAS), Piraeus (KODEP), Tilos (TILOS) and a consortium of municipalities in Crete (HDA) (UNHCR, 2019a).

Figure 3. Map of accommodation locations, October 2019 (UNHCR, 2019a).

As mentioned in the official website of the “ESTIA” programme, “urban accommodation provides a normal daily life for refugees and asylum-seekers in Greece, facilitates their access to services, including education, and the eventual integration for those who will remain in the country. The host population also benefits from embracing diversity through peaceful coexistence as well as the renting of their apartments”. Additionally, “cash assistance restores dignity and empowers refugees and asylum-seekers who can now

choose how to cover their basic daily needs. It also contributes directly to the economy of the host community through the purchase of services and goods” (ESTIA UNHCR, 2020). Over four in five accommodation places are in apartments and the rest in buildings.

By the end of October 2019, UNHCR had created 25,545 places in the accommodation scheme as part of the ESTIA programme. In total, since November 2015, 61,895 individuals have benefitted from the accommodation scheme. 21,585 people were accommodated as of the end of October 2019, 7,295 of whom are recognised refugees. 50% of the residents are children. The clear majority of those accommodated are families, with an average family size of five people. More than one in three residents present at least one of the vulnerabilities that make them eligible for the accommodation scheme. The clear majority, 88% of the individuals benefiting from the accommodation scheme, are Syrians, Iraqis, Afghans, Iranians or Congolese (DRC). However, the individuals accommodated as of the end of October 2019 speak over 30 different languages as a mother tongue (UNHCR, 2019a).

Figure 4. Nationalities of ESTIA beneficiaries, 31 October 2019 (UNHCR, 2019a).

According to a Ministerial Decision of 12 March 2019⁴¹ issued by the (former) Ministry of Migration Policy to regulate the ESTIA scheme, recognised refugees should leave these apartments after gaining protection status. Despite a number of exceptions in cases of extremely vulnerable groups, a large number of refugees are until today being forced to leave their apartments. The absence of a next step in terms of accommodation is the most prominent problem, related to both the long-standing absence of a social housing sector in Greece and the lack of an integration strategy. Serious concerns have been expressed through press releases regarding these evictions of refugees in Greece, and a variety of reports urge the Greek authorities to adhere to their obligations under international, EU and national legislation and ensure the minimum of a dignified and secure living for refugees (Leivaditi et al.,2020).

⁴¹ Ministry of Migration Policy Decision 6382/2019, Gov. Gazette 853/B/12.03.2019, available at: <https://bit.ly/2HJeiU8> (in Greek).

The majority of ESTIA beneficiaries were transferred to apartments from the five Northeastern Aegean islands where Hotspots are established. Thus, in their interviews they are able to compare reception practices and implementation

There is a huge difference, no comparison. [...] It gives me hope when I am inside society, with the local immigrants and other refugees. Little by little, I take my old life back, I have never before lived inside a tent or a box. The box I tell you about, the container, costs 20,000. People do not know that, with this 20,000, right now, at this moment of crisis, they can easily buy two buildings and accommodate the refugees or use the money that the state gives to rent the camps and spend it on houses. They can truly create a better life for the refugees and even more for the locals. That way the locals will not be afraid when they see the refugees. They will not be afraid when they see me, I left to escape from terrorist attacks, I did not come here to do this (Ermis).

Interviewees who are ESTIA beneficiaries did report some problems regarding issues of everyday needs in the apartments.

-Greece is a very good country and the Greeks are very good people, the house is good as well, but we have two problems. We have been placed with another family in one small house and the money we receive here in Greece cannot compare to what other refugees receive in other countries. [...]

-Does the house have heating?

-No, just some heaters [...] I want the two problems to improve, to receive a higher allowance and go to a house where we can be alone, things will be better. For my children”

More recently, given the absence of winterization plans for Hotspots and following the death of asylum-seekers in 2017 (Infomobile, 2017), an ad hoc program was implemented for the evacuation of large numbers of people from Hotspots to camps and hotels in the mainland. This decongestion program was implemented in 2017 with UNHCR assistance and provided a temporary solution (RSA-PRO ASYL, 2019:10). In October 2018, a new decongestion project was swiftly decided and put in place, receiving € 50,000,000 from DG Home emergency funding mechanisms, implemented until 30 November 2019. The project, named FILOXENIA (“Temporary Shelter and Protection for the Most Vulnerable Migrants in Greece”), is being implemented by the International Organization for Migration (IOM) and focuses on the fast-track creation of additional accommodation spaces throughout the Greek mainland (RSA-PRO ASYL, 2019:10-11). The programme aims at providing housing to 6,000 persons in hotels around the mainland, including Athens and the wider Attica region, the Peloponnese, Evia, Serres, Grevena, Thessaloniki, Kilkis, Kastoria and Asprovalta.

RSA and PRO ASYL have followed one case of a “Filoxenia” beneficiary and noted that “he was transferred to one of the FILOXENIA hotels on the mainland in March 2019, to a resort near the mountaineering centre in the Grevena region. The accommodation is isolated and one-and-a-half-hour drive away from the nearest city of Grevena. It is also far away from any services providing rehabilitation and support to victims of torture. Only once per week (on Fridays), a bus transports the hotel’s residents to Grevena where they can spend a few hours before returning to their accommodation” (RSA-PRO ASYL, 2019:12). According to RSA & PRO ASYL “the project started running without an integrated exit strategy on how and

where population offered accommodation in hotels will be re-directed after the winter. Hotels, although appropriate for an urgent project, are widely regarded as the overpriced choice when compared to projects that focus on establishing housing through rented flats, which can be implemented on a much slower pace” (2019:11). Additionally, “it is an example of how previous shortcomings of the reception system led to the adoption of needs for new expensive and temporary solutions that also carry flaws from their inception. This kind of solutions that, sooner or later, end up contributing to the problem” (RSA-PRO ASYL, 2019:2).

1.4 Informal types of accommodation and self-housing.

Apart from the types of accommodation and housing mentioned above, a number of refugees live in the large Greek cities and especially in Athens, informally, outside official policies and accommodation programmes. A number of them, especially those arriving before the EU-Turkey Statement when they could move freely to the mainland, live in rented apartments, particularly in central Athens. This self-housing practice usually applies for the asylum-seekers that can afford it. In the majority of the cases they live with friends, relatives or co-ethnics they met during their migration journey or during their permanence in other types of accommodation.

“I stay with my friend near to Victoria square. He is Afghani also, I found him because he is an interpreter in Arsis [...]. I found this job, then I called him [...] if you agree that we will live together because I can rent house. Yes, I rent the house” (Seralam).

“-When I was here, I didn't trust anyone, but when I left to Athens and saw the people there, I start to trust people.

-Where were you living in Athens?

-In Acharmon. You know Acharmon? Near Omonoia. I rent a flat. With other people, of course.

-How did you find it?

-I asked people there, because there are a lot of Arabic people there. I asked in Omonoia, in Acharmon. When I was in Athens, when I arrived, I went to a hotel to rent a room close to Omonoia. I just put my baggage in the room and then I left. And then I started to ask people. They gave me numbers and stuff like that, and then I started calling. Then I found a place and went there” (Jack).

Another type of accommodation should be mentioned: the squats or other spaces run by groups who stand in solidarity. A large number of squats in abandoned buildings operated in the central neighbourhoods of Athens until recently, accommodating numerous asylum-seekers and families. Their everyday needs were covered through common efforts of both the solidary groups and the asylum-seekers, while cohabitation trends between different ethnic and religious groups emerged from everyday life. Additionally, due to the central location of the squats, asylum-seekers became familiar with the neighbourhood they lived in and developed interethnic relationships with the locals.

“We spent a night in jail and, in the morning, they gave us some documents and took us to the train station, they bought us tickets and we arrived here, to Larissis

station (Athens]. When we got here it was 9 o'clock at night, we didn't know where to go, the child was crying and it was very cold. I have a cousin who lived in Athens for 15 years before moving to Canada. I bought a phone card for my mobile phone and called my cousin in Canada who speaks Greek well, and he spoke to some people who were at the metro station and asked them to help us get to a hotel. The next morning, we went to a school-squat in Acharnon. His cousin from Canada told him someone he knows spoke to him about the school-squat, and the same taxi driver who took us to the hotel came to pick us up the next morning and took us to the school. We stayed there for a month, and then, on the 1st of May, we marched to Parliament, all the refugees together, and the police came and threw us out" (Hafiz & Banek)

"Perfect, perfect! I've been staying at the [name of squat] for 5-6 months. Yes. I know the rest and now we are starting to learn Spanish and little by little I am learning to speak Arabic. Every day the Arab speakers are speaking English, Greek, and the children, I like the children a lot [...] I also like that it is close to the centre" (Ramon).

From spring to autumn 2019, following a governmental decision, the police evicted a large number of squats in central Athens and transferred the residents to camps in the mainland and to detention centres, depending on their legal status. Displaced from the central neighbourhoods of the city, where they had adapted and developed an urban everyday life, they were transferred again to remote areas, with poor connection to the cities and a lack of infrastructure. These evictions made the gaps in the reception system more obvious (RSA-PRO ASYL, 2019:12).

In general, destitution and homelessness remain matters of concern until today. The number of applicants who face homelessness is unknown. Homelessness is a serious risk for persons who have not been identified as vulnerable and are, thus, not eligible for accommodation under ESTIA, bearing in mind the lack of a clear referral pathway for mainland camps and the reported lack of capacity. Moreover, due to the poor conditions and the protection risks present in some of the camps, destitution cannot be excluded by the sole fact that an accommodation place is offered to one of them.

2. Early access to Education and the Labour Market

2.1 Education

According to Law 4540/2018 (article 13), asylum-seeking children have access to the education system under similar conditions as Greek nationals, and facilitation is provided in case of incomplete documentation as long as no removal measure against them or their parents is actually enforced. “Access to secondary education shall not be withheld for the sole reason that the child has reached the age of maturity” (Law 4540/2018, article 13). Registration may not take longer than 3 months from the identification of the child.

The Ministerial Decision 152360/ΓΔ4/2016 issued in August 2016 established a programme of afternoon preparatory classes (Δομές Υποδοχής και Εκπαίδευσης Προσφύγων, DYEP) for all school-age children aged 4 to 15. The programme is implemented in public schools neighbouring camps or places of residence. Children aged between 6-15 years and living in dispersed urban settings (such as UNHCR accommodation, squats, apartments, hotels and reception centres for asylum-seekers and unaccompanied children) may go to schools near their place of residence and enrol in the morning classes alongside Greek children at schools that will be identified by the Ministry (AIDA, 2019b). The role of the “refugee education coordinator” established by the Ministry of Education is extremely important; this is the person responsible for the coordination between the camps and the schools and is also in charge of a number of activities for asylum-seeking students.

Lessons conducted in the context of the DYEP programme do not take place during the regular morning programme of the public schools but during the afternoon, when the morning classes (for Greek students) are over. Due to this fact, a number of NGOs and organizations of education professionals have criticised the DYEP programme for not being inclusive, for promoting social segregation and for resulting in “ghetto schools”. As highlighted by the Greek Helsinki Monitor, “on 4 December 2017, the Panhellenic Scientific Union of Primary School Directors protested the continuing use of their school annexes, urging instead that the refugee children are integrated in the regular morning program through the use of the successful structure of Reception Classes” (GHM, 2018).

Despite the progress made on the implementation of the DYEP programme, low rates of school attendance among migrant children still exist. According to Refugee Support Aegean, during the 2017-2018 school year the number of children attending all levels of formal education was estimated at about 6,500 to 7,000, while the number of asylum-seeking and refugee children living in Greece during this period was approximately 20,000 (RSA, 2018a). In January 2019, the estimated number of refugee and migrant children in Greece was 27,000, among which 3,464 were unaccompanied children. Out of this number of children present in Greece, it is estimated that 11,700 refugee and migrant children of school age (4-17 years old) are enrolled in formal education.

The rate of school attendance is higher for children living in apartments and for unaccompanied children benefiting from reception conditions (66%) (AIDA, 2019b). Accordingly, access to education remains problematic for children in the Northeastern Aegean islands, a fact that has been repeatedly highlighted by a number of human rights actors, such as the Commissioner for Human Rights of the Council of Europe (Council of

Europe, 2018). Additionally, according to Human Rights Watch, “fewer than 15% of more than 3,000 school-age asylum-seeking children on the islands were enrolled in public schools at the end of the 2017-2018 school year”, while “only about 100 children, all preschoolers, had access to formal education” inside the RICs (HRW, 2018). In September 2018, migrant children in RICs on Lesbos, Chios and Samos did not have access to formal education, while less than 25% of the children remaining in the RICs of Leros and Kos had access to formal education (UNHCR, 2018c).

It should also be mentioned that Greek language classes are provided by universities and a number of civil society organizations or centres for vocational training. These include informal solutions inside the camps in the mainland organised by some NGOs (NCHR, 2016:14-15). In the case of Lesbos, a social centre located in Mytilene offers language courses to asylum-seekers residing in Moria Hotspot, as revealed by some interviews. Additionally, specific NGOs also provide language courses in Lesbos.

“-And all these months now, how is your everyday life here?

-If I wake up this morning, I go to school, Mosaik and after school...

-Every day?

-Monday, Tuesday, Thursday and Friday. 4 days per week I come here and then I go back. [...]

- I tell my psychologist, I tell him that I wanted to learn Greek, because I want to stay here. I want to continue my studies here in Greece” (Antoine).

“-So, did you start to take courses, educational courses? After how many months of being in the island?

-Yes, after six months. In Mosaik. We start with Greek. And then poetry, literature. I had a passion with literature. Kind of, you know, in my country most of the people they don't know how to speak English, for all my courses English was my first” (Willy).

Additionally, drawing from the experiences of interviewees residing in camps or apartments in the mainland, a wide range of different actors (specifically NGOs) providing language courses was revealed.

“I learned Greek in Greece, for a year now, at the university in Zografou, at Metadrasi, at Caritas organization in Omonoia, in Athens” (Ramon).

It should be also noted that the implementation of DYEP in the mainland led to a number of protests from groups that were against its operation in public schools. Racist narratives regarding the risk of “Greek students becoming infected by the refugees’ illnesses” emerged in specific schools in Attica and in other parts of Greece, with people even coming to blows in some cases. These events gained publicity through the press, mostly at the beginning of the DYEP programme but also during the following years, and conflicts and racist narratives continue to surface until today. A number of other actors, such as education professionals, NGOs and anti-racist organizations, reacted to these racist conflicts by safeguarding the continuation of the DYEP programme in the schools where the racist reactions took place (ELME, 2017).

2.2 Labour Market

According to Law 4540/2018 (article 15) and Law 4375/2016 (article 71) asylum-seekers can access the labour market as employees or service or work providers from the moment an asylum application has been formally lodged and they are thus in possession of the “international protection applicant card” or “asylum-seeker card”. Applicants who have not yet completed the full registration and lodged their application do not have access to the labour market. Regarding vocational training, Law 4540/2018 (article 17) provides that applicants can have access to vocational training programmes under the same conditions and prerequisites as foreseen for Greek nationals.

However, the effective enjoyment of access to the labour market is seriously hampered by the economic conditions prevailing in Greece, where unemployment rates remains high. In this very difficult context, asylum-seekers, especially those who do not speak Greek, have de facto limited chances of finding a job on the official labour market. Even though the unemployment rate dropped in 2018, it remained at 18.1% in November 2018 (down from 21.1% in 2017) while higher rates were reported for persons aged up to 34: 23.8% for age group 25-34 and 39.1% for age group 15-24 (ELSTAT, 2018).

Further challenges include administrative obstacles in obtaining necessary documents, which may lead to undeclared employment. In 2017, in order to reduce administrative obstacles to the provision of the Tax Registration Number (AFM) (without which one cannot legally work), the General Secretary of Migration Policy addressed a letter to the competent authorities, giving instructions for a proper implementation of the law. Moreover, as of February 2018, following a decision of the Hellenic Manpower Employment Organization (OAED), asylum-seekers willing to register themselves at the OAED registry can obtain a certification from the reception facility (AIDA, 2019c). Despite these positive developments, difficulties in obtaining an AFM number and unemployment cards from OAED are still reported.

Additionally, asylum-seekers face further obstacles to opening bank accounts, including those needed for receiving a salary. The four major banks in Greece have repeatedly refused to open bank accounts to asylum-seekers, even in cases where a certification of recruitment is submitted by the employer. Organization “Generation 2.0.” mentioned that “this policy offends against the spirit and the letter of the law, excluding thus the asylum-seekers from the labour market” (Generation 2.0, 2019).

Specific difficulties interrelated with the socioeconomic context in Greece were mentioned by interviewees in their experiences and narratives, such as the high levels of unemployment.

“- I was looking for jobs but there are no jobs. I tried to find any job, I don't care if it is a good or a bad job, I can't choose at this time, so if I get any job I'm ready to do it, but I was looking for job and I feel tired, you know, I give up. I asked any organizations, I have A.M.K.A, I.K.A, everything. I have everything of the document, but I couldn't find” (Robel).

Additionally, negative attitudes and prejudice by possible Greek employers have been reported.

“- I went to any institutions and I asked for job, sometimes they are not polite

-The locals?

- Yes, the locals, they shout at you, they say there is no job, get out of here. Yes, they don't want to listen to you, what you want, if you don't give up you will continue asking someone from here advise me to Google for a job for translation, I don't know, how can I apply because sometimes it is written in Greek and if I get a job here I don't want to leave to another country. Sometimes when you ask someone that is giving a job, I mean locals, they tell you that they are difficult for them to find a job. When you hear that you give up, but I think when you are a local you don't apply for a job, this is not good for me, I don't want to do it, but when you are a refugee you just want to focus on the money, not what job it is. But I think they didn't understand that, but when I have been informed that it is difficult for them also, I give up. And I just want to tell you something, I'm not asking for the favour, but if you can just find me any job, I'm ready to do it, any job, in a restaurant, in the hotel, anything if you can because I don't know how to apply for translation, any job, I'm telling you how difficult it is” (Robel).

Furthermore, when asylum-seekers do manage to find a job, this is usually in the most difficult sectors of the economy and in precarious conditions. For example, a significant number of asylum-seekers in Greece work in agriculture or in the industry and factories, usually in low-paid positions and working long hours. In their interviews, asylum-seekers also mention the big distance between the camps where they reside and their workplace as a problem resulting in long commutes.

“- But it's not easy to reach the restaurant because of the distance?

- Yes, because of the distance, because I was finishing my work late at night and I wasn't able to get there.

- Are the conditions good in the restaurant where you work?

- It's better, it's nice,

- How many hours do you work?

- About 12 hours every day” (Abdul).

“-Tell me a bit about your job, how did you find it, when did you begin and where is it?

-Oinofyta.

-When did you start working there?

-This year, six months ago, in June.

-What kind of job is it?

-It is a big company. A company, very big. It makes aluminium. We help, we clean the floor, the machines, everything. My friend who lives at the camp in Malakasa found it and I went. But I got AFM and AMKA since 2017, the other guys have only AMKA, no AFM. [...] I asked my lawyer to help me get the necessary documents to work. What to do. First AMKA and then AFM” (Ramon).

It should also be mentioned that a significant number of asylum-seekers who speak English apart from their native language have managed to find jobs as interpreters in NGOs or INGOs working on refugee issues.

“-Was it hard for you to find this work? How did you find the work?

-Through Caritas, I went there from Praxis. They told me that you should go to Caritas' office and they helped me in searching jobs, in finding jobs. Then I give my CV there. She told me that your cover letter shows you can work with us and since you speak five languages, so the job will be easy for you and there are many we can see what we can do. [...] She called me that she found a job for me and I applied and I forwarded my CV and cover letter to them. Then I went and they accepted.

-How is your work?

-[...] It's a kind of big organization, really good organization and they pay us and we help the people, a person should think about this. What I want I should want for the second brother, for other person. So, I really feel happy that I'm helping the people and if I can solve their problems by just only speaking by language... Yes, pleasure and, also, they pay us. So, they are satisfied" (Seralam).

In general, despite the fact that according to the relevant legislation, asylum-seekers can access the labour market, in practice they face a wide range of obstacles either due to the socio-economic situation of the country, or due to other institutional and bureaucratic factors as well as xenophobic perceptions. Moreover, even though significant numbers of asylum seekers and refugees seem to be absorbed by the rising economy of the humanitarian sector, this fact cannot of course reverse the wide range of remaining challenges regarding their employment opportunities.

3. Services and Allowances

The reception system in Greece except from the provision of accommodation includes as well the provision of food and non food items, medical support and specific types of allowances for the asylum seekers. In the context of the socio-economic crisis and following the above mentioned serious shortcomings of the accommodation system, services and allowances remain insufficient, without being able to cover the diverse needs of the asylum seekers.

3.1 Access to Health Care

As mentioned earlier, a significant number of the reception and hospitality facilities throughout Greece are located in remote areas, at a considerable distance from hospitals and other health care units. Persons belonging to particularly vulnerable groups are not systematically recognised as such and do not receive the specialised services and support they need, so they are exposed to serious risks. Such cases include pregnant women, unaccompanied minors, victims of torture and violence, people with disabilities or chronic illnesses, etc. Several published reports by humanitarian actors complain about the faulty/ineffective reception system of the country and report serious medical shortcomings inside the reception facilities, as well as serious medical and mental health conditions among a vast majority of asylum-seekers (ECRE, 2016; GCR, 2018; RSA-PRO ASYL, 2019).

In order to support its public health system structures, the Greek state adopted the “Comprehensive Emergency Health Response to Refugee Crisis”, aka PHILOS project, which mostly undertakes the burden of the “refugee crisis” as well as the responsibility to provide primary health care and mental health support services within camps in the mainland and in Reception and Identification Centres (RICs) on the islands (RSA-PRO ASYL, 2019: 6). The first phase of the health response project named “PHILOS 1” was implemented during 2016 and was entirely financed by the AMIF emergency assistance contributions (EC, 2019). PHILOS project was managed by the Ministry of Health and KEELPNO (Hellenic Centre for Disease Control and Prevention) which, in March 2019, was replaced by the National Organization for Public Health (HNPHO) (MOH, 2019). From the beginning of its implementation, the project faced serious challenges due to financial as well as bureaucratic constraints. A second version of the project, named PHILOS 2, was planned to begin around the first months of 2018. Efforts were made to tackle obstacles and limitations identified during 2016 and 2017, mostly to improve KEELPNO’s capacity to resolve the structural limitations in Hotspots as well as mainland camps (RSA-PRO ASYL, 2019: 6).

Since mid-2017, the medical screening and psychosocial assessment of newly arrived persons—taking place within the framework of reception and identification procedures in order to assess the potential of vulnerability—have been undertaken by KEELPNO. However, due to the severe understaffing of KEELPNO units at the RICs almost since the beginning of their operation, there have been major delays in the identification of vulnerabilities in newly-arrived persons in all the Northeastern Aegean islands.

According to our research participants, KEELPNO is indeed an understaffed service with almost permanent problems and a severe shortage of interpreters and doctors. Therefore, it is considered unable to respond to the increased needs in the field. This results in a lack of

access to medical assistance and significant delays in vulnerability assessments, which sometimes take place after the asylum interview has been conducted, in violation of the provisions of the relevant laws (Leivaditi et al., 2020). Additionally, some informants mentioned that people seeking asylum often have no access to interpreters during their vulnerability assessment. During the group interview with all the community leaders in Moria Hotspot, it was reported that one of the major problems facing KEELPNO is the lack of interpreters, as well as the long delays in appointments.

“The first problem is the asylum, KEELPNO is the first problem [...] KEELPNO is the first problem because they don't have [...] translators. When she goes over there, they'll give her one more time for 4 months later, then she'll go [...] one week later. So, the problem they face is translation. KEELPNO is not accepting any translators from inside Moria” (Group Interview).

The severe capacity shortages of KEELPNO have a serious impact on the asylum process in Greece, leaving large numbers of extremely vulnerable people trapped on the islands for long periods of time under harsh living conditions. The aforementioned lack of capacity has derailed vulnerability assessments on the islands, especially due to the absence of personnel in charge not only of conducting vulnerability screenings but also of signing the documents that certify such vulnerability (RSA-PRO ASYL, 2019, p. 9).

At the time that our research was being conducted in Lesvos and following a security incident in Moria Hotspot, KEELPNO had paused its activities as of 24/10/2018 for more than a month, denouncing the above mentioned shortage of staffing, the lack of interpreters, as well as the inadequate space. As a result, along with the absence of healthcare provision, vulnerability and age assessments could not be carried out at all. A huge backlog was created, significantly affecting asylum procedures in Lesvos and everyday life at the Hotspot.

Many interviewees reported serious issues in the vulnerability assessment procedures conducted by KEELPNO. Our interlocutors call the doctors of KEELPNO responsible for the vulnerability assessment “yes/no doctors” and denounce the limited provision of health care. “Yes” refers to those who will be recognised as vulnerable following the assessment, and “no” to those who will not be recognised as such and will therefore continue with the “Fast-Track Border Procedure” (AIDA, 2019d). Generally speaking, the provision of medical care in Moria seems to be limited to the vulnerability assessment.

“There is the doctor, we call him yes/no doctor. All the refugees they know about him like that. That you get yes or no. If you get yes, it's ok, if you get no, so you have to stay here (in Lesvos). There is this yes/no doctor and there are those who have big problems, so there is a psychiatrist doctor also. We call him doctor asap. Asap means brain... The situation is like this and specially for the doctors. There should be some doctors. Health is very important, I think. In Moria, if someone is going to die, no attention of doctor. Go and drink water, go and drink water” (Fatima).

Research participants also reported a serious lack of psychiatric and disability care in Moria Hotspot, as well as long and life-threatening delays in doctor appointments.

“Right now, there are people in need of psychiatric assistance who live in Moria, they either arrived with the disorder or acquired it in Moria due to the prevailing conditions. Right now, they wander like ghosts in there, given the lack of necessary

attention. The same applies for people with severe disabilities in need of round-the-clock attention, cases of autism, mental impairment, it's a dead-end" (Doctor working in a public hospital in Mytilene and former employee in INGO).

"The condition in Moria is very bad. It's not good. Moria, now, the doctors are not working. 3 weeks now. We have appointment to the week before, no doctor. Today again. Before I came here, I went again, no doctor. This is a problem. Very big. Around six months ago for example, he went to the doctor, he told I am not feeling well, I have a pain in my chest, they said you have nothing, he fell, and he died. Too many times I go to the doctor they say me I don't have a doctor, the second time, I don't have time, the third time, we can't write this medicine. Why?" (Group Interview).

A hospital doctor in Mytilene who used to work for an international NGO reports that:

"It is the inability not only of the asylum procedures but also of medical services to respond to the situation. These problems also exist in Athens, but there are more possibilities... There are cases of illness or necessary surgery that cannot be treated here and, although medical cases should be given absolute priority, the legal procedures and geographical restriction finally prevail. And even in cases where there is a clear diagnosis of someone who, for example, might lose a leg if he is not transferred to Athens to undergo surgery, there are significant delays, often with dire consequences for these people. The procedure is totally bureaucratic ... this system has no normality, it is ruled by the external factor of orders, decisions such as this month only 100 people can leave, for example, or no one... considering the volume of demands, it is chaotic, between the UNHCR, the Asylum Service, First Reception, the police, everything moves back and forth and is prioritized accordingly. It is all about how lucky someone will get and who he/she will encounter, if the person in charge will be quick to react..." (Doctor working in a public hospital in Mytilene and former employee in INGO).

There are attempts to cover the serious lack of state presence and the gaps of KEELPNO in the Hotspots by employing military doctors (there is usually one army doctor on call for hundreds or thousands of persons) or NGOs. Several NGOs provide medical triage and primary health care tasks including vaccinations throughout the reception and hospitality sites in Greece. However, they also face capacity shortages in their operations and, of course, they don't have the mandate to sign vulnerability assessments on behalf of the state. As a result, access to medical protection remains problematic and very limited, especially for those with chronic illnesses.

Since 2016, according to national legislation, asylum-seekers are entitled to free of charge access to necessary health, pharmaceutical and hospital care, including necessary psychiatric care where required. Law 4368/2016, which provides free access to public health services and pharmaceutical treatment for persons without social insurance and considered vulnerable, is also applicable for asylum-seekers and members of their families. However, actual access to health care services is hindered in practice by significant shortages in resources and capacity for both foreigners and the local population – as a result of the austerity policies followed in Greece – as well as the lack of adequate cultural mediators. The doctor interviewee reports that:

“We, too, receive so many cases that cannot be examined in Moria for lack of capacity... but we also must serve a big part of the Greek population. Of course, we will also attend to refugees. But when the number is so large... there is a problem in Moria, and especially during night shifts we have ambulances being used as means of transportation, bringing in cases that should normally be treated within the Moria Hotspot, if conditions were better and there were fewer people. But, of course, you cannot treat a centre with 10,000 persons, there is no such centre in Greece or anywhere else in Europe, I think. Can you control everything, security above all, which is so important, sanitary conditions, what can you control? And how can you put an order to things? I see this, they say ‘no doctor in Moria’ or I do not know when the doctor will see me. I understand my colleagues, they cannot treat everyone, it is impossible, or they have no medicine. But we do not have medicine here either, this is a public hospital and we do not have enough medicine, we try our best, but we don’t have medicine, we are a public hospital, you see there is a problem” (Doctor working in a public hospital in Mytilene and former employee in INGO).

Following the elections of July 2019, the new Greek government has stopped issuing social security numbers (AMKA) to third-country nationals, meaning that asylum-seekers are unable to access basic health services such as health care, psychological and psychiatric aid as well as vital medication except in emergencies. Therefore, asylum-seekers can now only access public hospitals as outpatient emergencies in the Emergency Departments of the Greek hospitals. As a result, chronically ill people are excluded from accessing the necessary and very costly medicine they need for their survival. It has to be mentioned that most of these drugs are usually very costly and are not provided by NGOs.

Participants expressed serious concerns regarding the impact of the crucial lack and inefficiency of medical and mental care provision on the lives of asylum-seekers.

There are also many cases where the violence emerges here, so vulnerability must be re-examined and also properly substantiated, or there might be a medical issue arising here or being diagnosed here, or cases of rape occurring here, all this requires a process of proper substantiation, because the people will not go themselves, they will not go and say this or that is going on, someone must dedicate time to them, substantiate everything, etc. [...] And the paradox is that, here, instead of people being protected we see people being retraumatised, there are physical and mental health problems that are created or aggravated here, there is rape and violence here and no one undertakes the protection of these people, a protection they truly need. Moria produces violence and traumatising experiences, and the system will not assume the responsibility” (Representative of “Lesvos Solidarity” NGO).

“If you are not sick, healthy, and you are coming, you are not sick mentally or physically, if someone is not sick, he is healthy. If you are coming from your country healthy, when you arrive here and you see this situation, how you live, how you get food, how you make your interview, how they treat, immediately you are (become) sick mentally or physically” (Robel).

“This is a case of institutional abuse. A situation is created that could be characterised as a condition of continuous traumatic stress. Continuous traumatic stress is differentiated from post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) in that it is not a

recognised disorder but rather an environment that constantly places you at risk of developing a more serious mental illness” (Psychologist, employee of an INGO).

Based on the aforementioned narratives, due to the inhuman living conditions in the reception facilities, vulnerability and violence emerge in-situ, even in the cases of asylum-seekers who didn’t have physical or mental health issues at the time of their arrival.

3.2 Provision of Food and Non-Food Items

The Council of Europe has deemed reception facilities in Greece to be substandard and able to provide no more than the most basic needs such as food, hygiene products and blankets (Council of Europe, 2018). However, in practice, even the aforementioned basic standards of human dignity are absent in several camps throughout the country.

“Instead of things getting better, it is getting worse and worse. People still live in tents, still complaining about the shower place, to take a shower, bathroom, food, asylum. Things that we used to complain 3 years ago. Like in 2016” (Kingslot).

Food provision in the reception camps around Greece is usually under the responsibility of the country's armed forces, but the rations and cash allowances are often substandard.⁴² Based on our fieldwork as well as on reports published by humanitarian actors, the food provided is insufficient and of very poor nutritional quality (HRW, 2016). Meals are usually cooked by private catering services and their cost is disproportionate. As regards the case of Moria Hotspot, the community leader of Arabs mentioned:

“They give you one croissant to every person only and they give you one bottle of mineral water in the day and you have to wait in the line for two hours”.

Moreover, food distribution remains a serious issue for the management of the majority of the reception facilities, as food often runs out before reaching the entire population. A lot of people do not systematically receive food on a daily basis, either because the food is not enough or because they are not able to wait for so many hours in the long queues just for a meal. In most of the camps in Greece, people are forced to spend their days waiting in queues just for the basic provisions.

“Everything there is a line. Food line, toilet line, doctor line. See? You must wait in the line again” (Antoine).

As our interlocutors informed us, residents in Moria Hotspot are supposed to wait in a queue for a minimum of two hours before the distribution of each meal starts. Nevertheless, even if they wait for so long, it is not sure that they will finally receive a food portion.

“And specially during the water line, food line, all the people know what is going on in food line. Everyday fighting because of the food line. In the morning we get one, like those who live in Moria. They get one cake with one bottle of water. For this line the people have to go in line at night, at 2 o'clock. They have to go in line and

⁴² Except from the cases in which food is not provided and, instead, asylum-seekers receive cash assistance from UNHCR.

stay, and next morning at 8:30 they give this cake and water. It means that half of their night they will spend it there. For one bottle of water and a cake. One day start distribution they start fight. Those who have large height they can take. Those who are smaller, like me, they cannot take anything. I am talking about my friend. She goes to food line at 2 o'clock, but in the morning she gets nothing. Always she gets nothing. She starts crying that she has nothing here and what should she do. No water, no cake. Her mother and sisters they come in (not clear). They do their breakfast in (not clear). And the food, for like lunch, they have to go at 11 o'clock in the line and wait until 2 o'clock. And for dinner they have to go at 4 o'clock until 7 o'clock at evening. Suppose that I got late, there is nothing for dinner for me. Everything is finished" (Fatima).

Queues in general, and especially for food, are additionally a primary cause for crucial tensions and fights among the residents, which often turn into mass conflicts between different nationalities.

"I stayed in Moria for ten days, afterwards we were attacked by some people. We didn't socialise with anyone but, because my daughter took two pieces of bread from the kitchen, some girls who worked at the kitchen took in my daughter and my daughter went and played with them, a game we call lime. There are also guys who are refugees, my daughter thought she was helping me that way, and she waited in line. I have not waited in line not even once, I never got food.

-Why?

-Because of the trouble. If you wait in line someone might attack you, you might quarrel with someone else, because there might also be gangs taking more food, water" (Ahmed).

However, in other accommodation camps the food is distributed door to door. According to our participants, it is, of course, much preferable than waiting in queues.

"They distribute at the doors. They have a list for each room and how many are staying there, and they provide at their home. Sometimes I feel that I am very lucky, I thank God that I live in here. At least I have not those problems, I am not suffering those problems in Moria" (Fatima).

The provision and distribution of non-food items is generally managed by NGOs in collaboration with the administration of each camp. However, there are often very serious shortages in non-food items as well, in hospitality sites in Greece and, mostly, in Hotspots.

"Moria is a very big problem. Very, very big problem, because I remained there for six months [...] They don't get clothes, etc. Then the new arrivals, one family gets just one blanket. In this cold weather. They have small children. How should they manage in cold? [...] I live in (another camp), if I have extra blanket, I can give them, but the director of the camp is not allowing this. He said that we are not allowed to distribute these things from one camp to another. But I have donated my 6 blankets. Rules are not important, but humanitarianism is more important for me. Because I have seen that mother, they were six family members and only had one blanket. And they have put this blanket below her baby. So, all the others were in the cold. They were in a tent without any blankets" (Fatima).

Overall, the fact that the majority of reception centres and Hotspots across the country have more or less surpassed their capacity, suffer from serious lack of funding, improper

planning and excessive bureaucracy, has serious impact on the provision of the relevant services.

3.3 Social Welfare and Allowances

As provided by Presidential Decree 220/2007, material reception conditions for asylum-seekers include accommodation in reception centres as well as a financial allowance. Moreover, according to Presidential Decree 141/2013 (art. 29, 30) beneficiaries of international or subsidiary protection in Greece should enjoy the same rights and receive the necessary social assistance according to the terms that apply to nationals, without discrimination (AIDA, 2019e).

In Greece there is a long-standing absence of mainstream welfare services and allowances for both foreigners and locals. Especially during the crisis, the overall welfare state was crucially affected by austerity measures and cutbacks in social services. A Social Solidarity Income (SSI) scheme was recently established as a primary social welfare measure in order to help the poorer population groups in the country who were severely affected by the crisis. The SSI can be granted to both Greeks and foreigners with no discrimination by law. Nevertheless, it is difficult to obtain due to its administrative and bureaucratic entry requirements (Mascall, 2018). In practice, not all beneficiaries have access to the mentioned social rights and welfare benefits due to bureaucratic barriers, which make no provision for individuals who are unable to submit certain documents such as family status documents, birth certificates or diplomas. Additionally, cases of civil servants refusing to grant the respective benefits have been reported, contrary to the principle of equal treatment as provided by law (Mascall, 2018).

Since April 2017, cash assistance has been delivered to asylum-seekers through the Greece Cash Alliance (GCA), a group of NGOs partnering with and led by the UNHCR, funded by the European Commission and cooperating with the (former) Greek Ministry of Migration Policy. In 2018, the GCA was led by UNHCR and comprised of Catholic Relief Services (CRS), in partnership with Caritas, the International Federation of the Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC) and the Hellenic Red Cross (HRC) (UNHCR, 2019b). According to UNHCR, this cash assistance program is provisional and its duration depends on the decision of the Greek authorities, the availability of funding as well as certain eligibility criteria which can change over time. In practice, after more or less six months of having received refugee status, the beneficiary will lose the entitlement to cash assistance and be considered self-reliant with the sole assistance of the aforementioned challenging social welfare system. Besides, cash assistance is very limited and cannot even cover a person's basic needs.

“-Once you receive an open card you need to spend 3, 2 months or 3 months to get cash from UNHCR. Yes, the monthly cash they give to us, and you need 3 months saving money, saving money to try to pay house with friends to live together.

-If you leave the island will you still receive the monthly cash?

-Yes, you will receive it. Even if you go to Athens alone.

-Even though you are not registered to the houses of UNHCR?

-Yes.

-For how long?

-Before, it wasn't possible, and now it's possible. 3 months or something like that" (Willy).

"...The money we receive here in Greece cannot compare to what other refugees receive in other countries. No, here in Greece the money is not enough. Not even for the babies, I have two babies, the diapers and milk cost 40 euros. And the milk is very expensive. 20 euro a box. I get 200 euro per month, it only pays for babies, the diapers, the milk, that is all. The baby presented some allergies, I took it to the dermatologist, the cream alone costs 15 euro. Winter is coming, we have no clothes, we will have to buy clothes" (Hafiz & Banek).

Apart from the beneficiaries of the ESTIA accommodation scheme, cash assistance is also provided to asylum-seekers residing in camps in the mainland. Based on our fieldwork, this cash assistance programme has limited capacity (in terms of staff) and, in most cases, there are long intervals between the date of arrival and the provision of case assistance.

"You're not allowed to go outside from your home for three years, you don't have television, you don't have money for anything, you don't have money to go to some restaurant and eat outside or go for a picnic or something, all you can do is stay in your home and do nothing. You'll get frustrated if you have to go to some meeting with Greek authorities or a lawyer. We have to find money ourselves, if you need 10 euros no, we ran out of money 3 days ago. With one of our friend we have to go to (the centre of) Mytilene, we have three euros, we ran out of money and we have five main things (to do) with five different organisations and we had no money to come back (for a bus ticket). The monthly is only 90 euros, we spend minimum 10 euros (for the necessary transportations), it is not enough. If you see families, they have 300 euros. You go to the doctor and you say my baby is sick but you don't have enough now. If you go and say that someone is ill or something, they give prescription and they say you can go to hospital and do a check-up and you have to spend your own money, they don't do it for free. If you go to doctor, they will give you medicine, 4 or 5 medicines in the prescription, you go to the market to buy for yourself, so how much will you spend?" (Group Interview).

4. Encounters with officials, civic actors and the receiving society

In this chapter we focus on the encounters with officials, civic actors and the receiving society. More specifically, we refer to the asylum seekers' access to legal assistance during the reception period, the role of local, national and international NGOs operating at the border and big Greek cities, as well as asylum seekers' perspectives with regard to the ways in which the receiving society do, or do not, welcome them. A special attention is given to asylum seekers' and refugees' experiences of racist perceptions and practices from a part of the local population.

4.1 Officials

Following the Asylum Procedures Directive⁴³, the Greek legislation stipulates *inter alia* the provision of information and legal support to asylum-seekers regarding the procedure to be followed, their rights and obligations in a language they understand. According to Presidential Decree 220/2007 (art. 3), the competent authorities are supposed to inform each applicant immediately and, in any case, within 15 calendar days, providing them with informative material on their legal rights in a language that they understand. This material must provide information on the existing reception conditions, including health and medical care, as well as on the operation of UNHCR in Greece and other organizations that provide assistance and legal counselling to asylum applicants. If the applicant does not understand any of the languages in which the information material is published or if the applicant is illiterate, the information must be provided orally with the assistance of an interpreter. A relevant record must, in such case, be kept in the applicant's file. In practice, while newcomers transfer to the RICs, the RIS undertakes their initial briefing on rights and obligations, which is then followed-up by a second information session conducted by UNHCR field-based teams (usually 10-15-minute group sessions). These sessions commonly take place too soon after their arrival, a few hours after their rescue at sea, at a time when they are exhausted, frustrated and, of course, not in a position to understand the content of the provided information.

According to Ministerial Decision 12205/2016 regulating the state-funded legal aid scheme, asylum-seekers must request legal aid at least 10 days before the date of examination of the appeal under the regular procedure, while shorter time limits are foreseen for the Admissibility Procedure, Accelerated Procedure and Fast-Track Border Procedure. If a legal representative has not been appointed at the latest 5 days before the examination of the appeal under the regular procedure, the applicant may request a postponement of the examination (AIDA, 2018: 57). As such, legal aid is provided only for appeal procedures and remains limited in practice, thus applicants often have to navigate the complex asylum system on their own, without sufficient information (UNHCR, 2018d). In 2018, most appellants did not have access to the legal aid scheme. Out of a total of 15,355 appeals lodged in 2018, only 3,351 (21.8%) asylum-seekers benefited from the state-funded legal aid scheme" (AIDA, 2018: 58).

⁴³ Asylum Procedures Directive 2013/32/EU. [online] Available at: <https://bit.ly/2Zc2oYI> [Accessed 18 December 2019]

No state-funded legal aid is provided for other procedures regarding the asylum application, including the examination of the application at first instance and the judicial review of second-instance decisions. Consequently, a significant number of NGOs provide legal advice and legal assistance in asylum procedures, usually based on the availability and their presence throughout the country. Over 10,000 asylum-seekers and beneficiaries of international protection received services such as counselling, assistance and legal representation in asylum procedures and other issues relating to access to rights by NGOs under UNHCR funding in 2018 (AIDA, 2018:55-56).

Although a number of actors are engaged in the provision of legal aid both in the Northeastern Aegean islands and in the mainland, they still remain insufficient to address the needs of asylum-seekers. The fluidity of the operational context (new arrivals, constant changes in legislation and practice, bureaucratic hurdles as well as severe shortages in the legal aid operations) render access to comprehensive information and legal assistance an ongoing matter of concern in Greece.

Culturally and linguistically appropriate legal support at first instance is also crucial, due among others to the frequently changing policies and procedures and to the insufficient information available to applicants going into their first interview. Legal counselling at second instance often comes too late to ensure that the legal rights of the asylum-seekers have been respected in the first instance (ActionAid et al., 2017).

A wide range of information gaps have also been observed in the field. Our research participants often did not know exactly at which step of the procedure they were, or couldn't understand the meaning of the status they had already gained.

“-I received the answer of my interview yesterday. My decision.

-And what's your status now?

-My status is... I can't memorise, can I read it to you? My status is subsidiary protection [...]. It's [...], not refugee” (Aynla).

According to a UNHCR interagency participatory assessment in 2018 based on a sample of 1,436 persons: “The majority of participants were frustrated with what they consider a lack of sufficient information on asylum procedures and the legal framework. A particular source of anxiety is the lack of clarity on procedures or feedback on the status of their asylum claim, particularly on the islands. This has severe implications on psycho-social wellbeing, irrespective of age and gender. [...] Participants in most Focus Group Discussions noted difficulties accessing information. This included a lack of interpreters for certain languages (e.g. Somali, Farsi, Kurmanji, Panjabi, Bangla, Urdu, Sorani, Amharic, Tigrinya, etc.) and the lack of consistent and simplified information on services and procedures. This applies to sites, RICs and urban locations and to information provision upon arrival. [...] Communication materials are often too difficult to understand or not translated in all relevant languages” (UNHCR, 2018b).

4.2 Civil society actors

Since the beginning of the so-called refugee crisis, the Greek state has increased its reliance on the assistance of operational actors, especially International Organizations and NGO's. Asylum-seekers in Greece are dependent on partial services offered by the NGOs that remain active either on the islands or in the mainland. It is worth noting that, in 2018, there were 114 NGOs with 7,356 "volunteers" operating only in Lesbos (European Parliament, 2018b). Bringing these actors together to respond in a coherent manner constituted a significant challenge because the lack of integrated planning as well as the challenging coordination and communication between the involved key stakeholders. It has taken time to ramp up coordination between the different International Organizations and NGOs as each has its own internal priorities and procedures. Our research participants, as well as reports from NGOs and INGOs, mention how the development of operational working methods is strongly influenced by specific needs on the ground (ActionAid et al., 2017). Moreover, the development of modes of coordination also differs from site to site or from Hotspot to Hotspot, mainly due to the fact that it often remains unclear who the ultimate decision maker is.

Coordination still seems crucial at several levels, from high-ranking political direction to policy and technical coordination and down to implementation of policies in the field. At the same time, response to increased needs since 2015 spanned different policy areas and often required the expertise and resources of the Ministries of the Interior and of Foreign Affairs, as well as of the humanitarian agenda of the EU and of national governments.

The poor and disorganised networking among humanitarian actors causes the duplication of efforts, overlapping, time inefficiencies and conflicting strategies. Another major challenge is that most NGOs lack a cohesive and long-term strategic plan that could provide appropriate support to people of concern. NGOs usually struggle to obtain grants and donors, especially because they typically don't have enough capacity for fundraising and outreach. However, donations and funding are absolutely essential for the provision of their services and, of course, for the continuing of their operations.

A wide range of participants from micro level interviews complain that the existing humanitarian projects provided by NGOs are either limited in outreach or of a small scale, and as a result the provision of services is considered ineffective and limited.

"I visit any organization, they just want my name. I was asking something, and they just promised me and then I asked to provide me house and then they registered my name, my phone number and they told me that they would call me just how they promised, just promises" (Ahmed).

"When you go to them and say help, I need this thing or that, they give you appointment, they always give appointment, even if you are sick. If you are sick and you need emergency help, they give you appointment. They always give appointment, long appointment" (Aynla).

The distinction made by some interlocutors between the NGO headquarters and NGO workers was also very interesting.

“I don't think I got any support from NGOs. I think most of the support that I got, it was from the Greek people, not the Greek government. Those people that were working in the organizations they support me. They give us a place to sleep, giving food, giving me materials to continue my art job school. But they don't have good headmaster, it's a problem of ruling in my opinion, those that are the head of these organizations are not the best people” (Faz).

Last but not least, participants noted a lack of programmes to encourage coexistence with the host community across the country, even more so in sites and RICs, as well as a general lack of a community-based orientation of humanitarian operations, relevant to the needs of the people of concern.

“There are NGOs but they are NGOs. They are Dutch NGOs, Swiss NGOs, English NGOs, OK, we need them, but we don't need them that much. If you are living here, if you are gonna live your life in Greece, we need Greek, not English (NGOs)” (Kingslot).

“I want to tell you something, it's like if you want to know what is this, nobody asks a refugee what is good for him, what he wants. The most nobody, you see even NGOs, they pretend to help us, but they don't ask. They come with their projects, they said that, okay, we think that those people will need these, they come with their project without asking us. You see, they will come with respect, oh let's talk, what do you need the most, you talk, you interact, and then they come with their project and they make you part of their project but a refugee no. Somebody said that, okay, a refugee in the camp don't have enough showers, let's make showers for refugees without asking them” (Penen).

The coordination challenges between the different actors, the instability of the humanitarian operations, the lack of funding, as well as the lack of community-based orientation of the provided services have a serious impact to the establishment of trust between the asylum seekers, refugees and (I)NGOs. Moreover, the aforementioned issues strengthen as well the overall inadequacy of the reception system in Greece.

4.3 Experienced “welcome culture” and racist perceptions and practices

Since the beginning of the so-called refugee crisis, a considerable part of Greek society responded spontaneously with empathy towards the new-comers passing through the country, and often engaged in practices of solidarity (such as donations of goods or money). However, this massive wave of solidarity of the first years later receded, giving also space to xenophobic discourses.

At the same time, racist attitudes, prejudices and even racist violence still prevail in different contexts all over the country (RVRN, 2018). The role of the media in reinforcing racist narratives in Greece is crucial. Additionally, politically conservative and racist discourses have always been reproduced by political parties, official institutions and media actors alike, even before the beginning of the so-called refugee crisis. The practices of racist

violence in local contexts were strengthened since the electoral win of neo-Nazi organisation Golden Dawn (GD) and exist until today, even after the electoral defeat of GD in the recent 2019 national elections (Kandylis and Kavoulakos, 2011). As the coordinator of the Racist Violence Recording Network noted recently, there is an alarming expansion of racism and a continuation of the culture of violence in the neighbourhoods (Vima, 2019).

Based on our fieldwork, some of the research participants in Lesvos island reported limited interaction with locals, while others from both the micro and meso level referred either to welcome and supportive behaviours as well as to xenophobic behaviours or racist practices.

“People are very helpful, I have often asked for directions on the street and they have helped me, I wave hello, they have no problem. The people are good, there are others from the shops who know me, they say hello, I buy things, sometimes I see other workers and I say hello and they wave back and there is no problem, but there are others who are not good” (Amin).

“Lesvos, it's a nice island, it's a beautiful island, so many things to discover. Actually, I love the people here, they are super nice. They are like neutral people. If you talk, they talk. If you are not talking, they won't talk. So, I love that kind of people. And everyone is busy with their own life. Like here, this is what I like about them, they don't talk about you so much. Maybe there is always good and bad, even (among) refugees, have good and bad people” (Kingslot).

However, the same interviewee, in a next stage of our discussion, referred to a xenophobic and racist incident that took place in the capital of Lesvos, Mytilene.

“Did you ever face any bad behaviour from the locals here or anywhere?”

-I faced in Cosmote (local telephone company), I went there to the shop to buy a SIM card for me and the guy asked for my ID and I gave it to him, and he was like "Can you go outside of the shop, and I will call you when it's ready". Sorry, what did you just say, if I can wait outside? You are joking, right? I am the customer. So, I told him like, if you are telling a customer to go and wait outside, this is not polite and this is not written in any book, like in any corner of the world. Imagine how many people a day is giving this behaviour!

-What did he answer?

-He was quiet, he didn't answer anything. He didn't answer, he didn't spoke to me, just took my name, gave me my SIM card, and sent me to pay. That's all. But this is how it is. Small thing. Small problems. But if you start noticing the small problems we cannot be together anymore. Someone should quit and say OK. Instead of argument. If we always argue no one gonna with it. So, someone need to say OK, it's fine. Because the people create hate in their hearts. It's just like, I don't know. But once you leave your home everything is possible”.

“-And how is the experience of living in Lesvos with the locals, the local community?”

-The people is not change but more of them, I think, their faces is not good when they see you. They don't give you a good face. I think they understand, they are giving a bad feeling when they see. But there are good people, not all of them” (Aynla).

These complex and differentiated perceptions were also reported in the meso-level interviews.

“There is a general impression that the refugee issue is a problem, that refugees are a problem and a threat to the local community, that those who are employed in this field and in NGOs are those who take the money and do not care about the local community, all this generalization. The island (Lesvos) did not initially have a loud and aggressive reaction towards refugees from before, there were no organized voices against refugees. However, there have been refugees on the island since 2001, there was a detention centre until 2009 with awful conditions, no one knew about it and people lived there in horrible conditions and we put up with them. We do not take up arms against the refugees, but the fact that you know what is going on in a detention centre and you tolerate it, that means something. The fact that in 2015 all the solidarity, which was not all spontaneous but there was indeed a lot of support by the people, the fact that the media largely projected the support of the people... Even if there were many exceptions, people mostly showed their support and there was a generalized climate that solidarity is something positive, going out and helping others. But this was always borderline, for there was also a lot of misery and we also put up with it. The conditions in Moria were and are miserable, thousands live among the rubbish and the situation is tragic... And some tried to make money out of all of this, and indeed did make money. Some political forces also try to use the refugee issue to gain votes, they project an anti-refugee discourse and try to make refugees responsible for all the island’s problems and dangers. This has obviously influenced some people. The fact that the situation is the way it is in Moria and there is no reaction by the local community... reaction against the fact that there are people living in these conditions, with everything we know, there is none... So, I think that is where we stand right now, and there is also one factor which has an important role to play, that of politics. That is, the political discourse that will be articulated and used in one direction or the other”. (Representative of “Lesvos Solidarity” NGO)

On 22 April 2018, an overnight violent racist attack took place in Lesvos, an incident which is reported as one of the darkest nights in the recent history of migration in Greece. At that time, asylum-seekers from Moria Hotspot were protesting being trapped on the island under inhuman conditions, and they were attacked by groups of extremists and locals in the central square of Mytilene. At that night, at least 28 refugees were transferred to the public hospital with head injuries, panic attacks and respiratory problems caused by police teargas. Despite the fact that the Attorney General of Mytilene was present from the beginning of the event, no locals were arrested by the police. Instead, 120 Afghans were accused of intimidation and occupation of public space (Refugee Observatory, 2019).

“Many people of Afghan origin, including families and others, went from Moria to the town’s central square and started a hunger strike. The incident that sparked the protest was the death of an Afghan man in Moria who had not received adequate medical assistance. Their demands obviously included their transfer to the mainland (a lifting of the geographical restriction), advancement in the asylum procedures, an issuing of decisions and freedom from the island. The refugees were finally attacked by young and not-so-young locals with bottles, water, plastic objects, stones, fires were lit, the refugees and those who stood in solidarity with them were chased around the surrounding streets and in refugee-friendly cafés.

People were injured and taken to hospital. At about 6 in the morning the police wagons came, the attackers receded, and the refugees were arrested” (employee of a Greek NGO).

Several practices of racism and xenophobia, such as anti-refugee protests and night-time racist attacks, have been repeatedly reported within the Greek territory, in urban centres, in the islands as well as in mainland regions where reception facilities operate (RSA, 2018b). Participants of the micro level interviews shared personal experiences of racist violence in Athens, while others intentionally avoided referring to similar incidents.

“It was the 17th of November and I was the victim of a fascist attack, I had problems with my head and was afraid in general, I didn’t want to go out so I wouldn’t suffer a second one and I gave up. The first time was under my house, about ten people hit me, now I cannot hear from the right ear, it is a vein in the head which swells up when you are hurt and it swells up and fills with blood, they were wearing t-shirts and holding flags. I went to the central police station and made a report. This happened in Amerikis sq., the first attack was in 2017, 19 November 2017, and the second one in August 2018 in Kamatero, they started swearing at me, but people came out and didn’t let them attack me, they started shouting get out of here, what do you want, it’s one kid on his own...” (Ermis)

Last but not least, apart from the racist violence, there have also been many reports and press releases regarding serious labour exploitation and violent incidents committed by employers against the foreign employees. These reports refer to cases of asylum-seekers, refugees or migrants not receiving proper salaries, lacking basic means of subsistence, receiving death threats or even being subjected to physical violence when claiming their benefits (Council of Europe, 2018).

Conclusions and Policy Recommendations

This report is part of the fourth Work Package of RESPOND and deals with issues of refugee reception. By the term “refugee reception” we referred to the EU’s ensemble of legislation, policies, implementation practices, institutions, and actors concerned with defining, conceptualizing and implementing reception in Greece. Even though the time frame of “reception” is not clearly defined in EU legislation, in our working understanding, reception refers to the liminal period between the arrival and application for asylum and the issuing of a decision on the asylum application. In this report, the analysis drew from a wide range of published reports and from the empirical research evidence on the experiences, perceptions and actions of actors and asylum-seekers.

Regarding the legal framework on reception, significant recent developments were presented in the relevant section entitled “Policies and Legal Regulations of Reception”. The most important development was the adoption of Law 4540/2018 that amended the Greek legislation in accordance with the provisions of Directive 2013/33/EU on the standards required for the reception of applicants for international protection.

The chapter entitled “Policies of Reception” was based on existing practices and responses at the grassroots level. It has thus drawn from the gathered empirical research evidence and, more specifically, interviews with refugees and actors involved in the field (micro and meso level). In this chapter, we reflected on the implementation of refugee reception by focusing on the following themes: Accommodation and Housing (Accommodation in Hotspots, camps, in the urban space through the ESTIA scheme and informal housing); Early Access to Education and the Labour market; Services and Allowances (Access to Health Care, Provision of Food and Non-Food Items and Social welfare and Allowances), and Encounters with Officials, Civic Society Actors and the Receiving Society.

Significant observations emerge from the analysis, as specific problems and challenges persist in the reception system in Greece. Regarding accommodation for asylum-seekers in the Northeastern Aegean islands, the situation has been widely documented and remains extremely alarming. The imposition of the “geographical restriction” on the islands since the launch of the EU-Turkey Statement has led to significant overcrowding in the reception facilities. Prevailing reception conditions, particularly in the Hotspots, may reach the level of inhuman, as the basic needs and human rights of asylum seekers are threatened and violated on an everyday basis. As regards to camps, mainly in mainland Greece, one of the most important negative characteristics is the fact that they are usually established in remote areas, outside the urban environment, at a significant distance from the closest cities and without adequate transportation, resulting in the spatial segregation of the asylum-seekers remaining there. Additionally, it has been mentioned that the camps are not per se suitable for long-term accommodation. The numerous differences in reception conditions between the RICs and the camps in the mainland, but also between different camps in the mainland, consolidates inequalities in housing conditions. Accommodation in the urban space through the UNHCR accommodation scheme “Emergency Support to Integration and Accommodation programme - ESTIA” can be highlighted as a good practice, but it should be expanded to host a larger number of asylum-seekers and not just the vulnerable categories

of the respective population. The limited capacity of the ESTIA scheme, as well as the lack of a well-prepared next housing step for recognised refugees, could reproduce homelessness among a large number of refugees.

Except for the insufficient living conditions forced upon asylum-seekers in the Greek reception system, there are also serious shortcomings regarding early access to education and the labour market. Despite the progress made on the implementation of the DYEP programme, low rates of school attendance among migrant children still exist. As regards employment, despite the letter of the law, asylum-seekers and especially those who do not speak Greek have de facto limited chances of finding a job on the official labour market. Additionally, they face a wide range of administrative obstacles in order to obtain the necessary documents, a situation that may lead to undeclared employment or unemployment.

Furthermore, there are still serious problems regarding Services and Allowances in terms of access to health care and medical and psychosocial support, especially in the Hotspots on the Northeastern Aegean islands but also in camps in the mainland. The significant understaffing of the respective actors has been a problem widely reported in recent years, one that, in the case of the Northeastern Aegean islands, has led to major delays in the identification of vulnerabilities among new arrivals. As regards to the provision of food and non-food items, even basic needs such as food, hygiene products and blankets are often not covered. The fact that most reception centres and Hotspots across the country have more or less surpassed their capacity, suffer from serious lack of funding, as well as improper planning and excessive bureaucracy has a serious impact on the provision of services and the overall management. Additionally, in terms of services and allowances, the poor Greek welfare state that was also affected by the austerity measures during the crisis has proven inadequate to cover the relevant needs. Even though there is no discrimination by law, asylum-seekers and refugees are usually excluded from specific allowances due to administrative and bureaucratic entry requirements, while cash assistance for asylum-seekers refers, to present, to a limited number of beneficiaries.

Regarding the different actors implementing reception policies, a large number of International Organizations and NGOs have been assisting the Greek state since the beginning of the so-called refugee crisis, but coordination between them remains problematic. Differentiated perceptions of asylum-seekers have arisen regarding the reception work done by these organizations. Additionally, in terms of the relations of asylum-seekers with the receiving society, a range of different perceptions, attitudes and practices emerged which range from a “welcome” culture of solidarity to racist practices and violence that prevail in Greece until today.

Concluding this report, it is important to remind the shifting Greek political context at the time of its writing. To the extent that a wide range of conservative measures on refugee issues have been mostly announced but also implemented, the issues pertaining to refugee reception in Greece are considered to be once again under transition and transformation, highlighting yet another time the crucially temporary and fluid character of the subjects examined.

Table 3: Policy Recommendations

- End of the EU “Hotspot Approach” and respect of the right to live in dignity.
- End of the geographical restriction and immediate disengagement of the islands of the Northeastern Aegean by the transfer of asylum-seekers to the mainland.
- Significant increase in accommodation facilities both in the mainland and in the Northeastern Aegean islands.
- Immediate upgrade of the Reception and Identification Service with sufficient staff and resources.
- Strengthening of the camps with medical and paramedical staff as well as logistics staff for the improvement of conditions and services, including medical and psychosocial support and cultural mediation.
- Appropriate allocation of shelter through gender separation to avoid women being forced to share shelter with unknown males, increase security and lighting in the camps.
- Strengthening and expansion of the capacity of the “Emergency Support to Integration and Accommodation programme - ESTIA” to host larger number of asylum-seekers in the urban space in Greece.
- Direct connection of the ESTIA programme with the HELIOS integration programme regarding the accommodation of recognised refugees in order to prevent homelessness.
- Education and employment policies in order to enable the transition to self-reliance.
- Full respect for the rights of the individual in accordance with the letter and spirit of human rights law, international humanitarian law and refugee law.
- Free access to legal counselling and representation. On-time legal advice, preferably through personal contact with assigned caseworkers and lawyers.
- Assurance that procedural guarantees, including access to legal representation and legal aid in decisions surrounding any deprivation of liberty, are fully implemented.
- Ensure the rights of vulnerable refugee groups by providing an integrated network of adequate services.

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Appendices

Table 4. Camps in mainland Greece, September 2018 (UNHCR, 2018a).

Open Reception Facilities (sites):						
No.	Administrative Regions:	Name:	SMS agency:	Date of update:	Population:	Estimated # of available places:
1	Attica	Elefsina	IOM	2018-09-06	127	0
2	Attica	Eleonas	-	2018-09-04	1,470	0
3	Attica	Lavrio (Min. Agr. Summer Camp)	DRC	2018-09-07	248	4
4	Attica	Malakasa	IOM	2018-09-11	1,276	0
5	Attica	Schisto	DRC	2018-09-05	819	7
6	Attica	Skaramagas Port	DRC	2018-09-18	1,918	0
7	Central Greece	Oinofyta	IOM	2018-09-11	596	39
8	Central Greece	Ritsona (A.F. Camp)	IOM	2018-09-11	853	0
9	Central Greece	Thiva (Sakiroglou)	IOM	2018-09-07	804	0
10	Central Greece	Thermopiles	IOM	2018-09-11	518	0
11	Central Macedonia	Alexandria (G. Pelagou Camp)	DRC	2018-08-15	712	0
12	Central Macedonia	Diavata (Anagnostopoulou Camp)	ASB	2018-09-21	816	0
13	Central Macedonia	Kato Milia	IOM	2018-09-12	302	32
14	Central Macedonia	Lagadikia	DRC	2018-08-15	368	0
15	Central Macedonia	Nea Kavala	DRC	2018-08-15	765	42
16	Central Macedonia	Serres (Former KEGE)	IOM	2018-09-11	649	0
17	Central Macedonia	Vagiochori	IOM	2018-09-11	348	0
18	Central Macedonia	Veria (Armatolou Kokkinou Camp)	DRC	2018-08-15	311	4
19	East Macedonia and Thrace	Drama (Industrial Zone)	IOM	2018-09-11	328	4
20	East Macedonia and Thrace	Kavala (Perigiali)	IOM	2018-09-06	390	0
21	Epirus	Doliana	ASB	2018-09-24	115	0
22	Epirus	Filipiada (Petropoulaki Camp)	ASB	2018-09-24	487	104
23	Epirus	Katsikas	ASB	2018-09-24	437	545
24	Thessaly	Koutsochero (Efthimiopoulou Camp)	DRC	2018-09-10	1,423	0
25	Thessaly	Volos	DRC	2018-09-19	143	4
26	West Greece	Andravida	IOM	2018-09-06	235	0
Total					16,458	785

Table 5. Camps on the islands in Greece, September 2018 (UNHCR, 2018a)

Open Reception Facilities (sites):						
No.	Administrative Regions:	Name:	SMS agency:	Date of update:	Population:	Estimated # of available places:
1	Lesvos	Kara Tepe	-	2018-09-03	1,219	10
2	Leros	PIKPA	-	2018-09-13	65	45
Total					1,284	55

Figure 5. Statistics on Gender and Age Disaggregation in camps, October 2019 (IOM, 2019).

Figure 6. Statistics on Nationality Breakdown in camps, October 2019 (IOM, 2019).

Table 6. Micro-level interviewees: Pseudonyms and personal information

Micro-level Interviews							
Pseudo-nyms	Age	Civic status	Date of arrival in Greece	Gender	Legal status	Nationality	Point of Arrival in Greece
Kingslot	25	Single	07/2016	M	subsidiary protection	Afghan, Born & Raised in Pakistan	Lesvos
Ahmed	32	Married with family	Not Applicable	M	Asylum Seeker	Palestinian, Born and lived in Syria	Lesvos
Amin	27	Single	11/2015	M	Asylum Seeker	Afghan, Born & Raised in Iran	Kos
Abdul	26	Engaged in Afghanistan	04/2017	M	Asylum Seeker	Afghan	Lesvos
Syrian Refugee	18	Single	Not Applicable	F	Applicant for Family Reunification	Syrian	Lesvos
Aynla	20	Single	04/2018	M	subsidiary protection	Somalia	Lesvos
Izzy	25	Not Applicable	10/2008	M	Asylum Seeker	Afghan	Lesvos
Jasmid	28	In relationship a	2008	M	subsidiary protection	Afghan, Born & Raised in Iran	Lesvos
Libeex	24	Single	2018	M	Asylum Seeker	Somalia	Lesvos

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Michael	35	In relationship	04/2008	M	Asylum Seeker	Sudan	Lesvos
Mohammad	18	Single	12/2016	M	International Protection	Syrian	Lesvos
Nam & Mohammad	45 & 32	Married with family	09/2018	M & F	Asylum Seekers	Iraq	Lesvos
Ermis	18	Single	03/2016	M	Applicant for Family Reunification	Afghan, Born & Raised in Iran	Lesvos
Penen		Not Applicable	05/2017	M	Asylum Seeker	Congo	Lesvos
Ramon	22	Single	10/2016	M	Asylum Seeker	Born in Afghanistan, lived in Pakistan & Iran	Chios
Thanasis - Mah	23	Single	2016, before the EU-Turkey Deal	M	International Protection	Afghan, Raised in Iran	Chios
Wael	20	Single	10/2015	M	Refugee-Residence permit	Syrian	Lesvos
William	18	Single	07/2018	M	Asylum Seeker	Burundi	Lesvos
Willy	24	Single	1/2018	M	Asylum Seeker	Cameroon	Lesvos
Arif & Nemen	30 & 24	Married with 2 children	07/2017	M & F	Asylum Seekers	Kurds from Syria	Kastelorizo & Kos

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Mohsin & Lima	26 & 21	Married with 2 children	04/2018	M & F	Asylum Seekers	Syrians	Alexandrou-polis
Medin & Farus	23 & 23	Married with 2 children	04/2018	M & F	Asylum Seekers	Kurds from Syria	Lesvos
Hafiz & Banek	29 & 23	Married with 2 children	04/2018	M & F	Asylum Seekers	Kurds from Syria	Alexandrou-polis
Anonymus	32	Single	2009	M	International Protection	Afghan, Lived some years in Iran	Lesvos
Antoine	31	Single	06/2017	M	Asylum Seeker	Guinea	Lesvos
Fatima	24	Single	11/2017	F	Asylum Seeker	Afghan, Lived in Pakistan	Lesvos
Faz	21	Single	30/03/2016	M	Not Applicable	Iran	Lesvos
Jack	21	Single	03/2017	M	Asylum Seeker	Iraq	Lesvos
Costas	37	Married with family in Russia	06/2013	M	Asylum Seeker	Burundi	Lesvos
Robel	24	Single	09/2017	M	Asylum Seeker, applied for 2nd instance	Eritrea	Lesvos
Seralam	26	Single	06/2018	M	Asylum Seeker	Afghan	Alexandrou-polis

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Group Interiew	1.34, 2.23, 3.16, 4.23, 5.55	1.2.5. Married with family, 3.4. Married together	Unassigned	1.2.3.5. M., 4.F	Asylum Seekers	1.Afghan, 2.Pakistan, 3.4. Iran, 5. Iraq	Lesvos
Norouh	21	Single	Unassigned	M	Asylum Seeker	Afghan	Lesvos
Rehma	48	Single	08/2017	M	Asylum Seeker	Syrian	Lesvos